

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

M6.2 Preliminary Results of the DSS for the Case Study Site

VERSION 1

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

This milestone, namely M6.2, is part of Task 6.2 “Results of the DSS for the case study sites under future scenarios” (Lead TUC, participants: UPV, UFZ, UNIPR, CERTE and BU), (Month 12 – Month 36). The aim of M6.2 is to present the results of the simulation – optimization (S – O) procedure for the Tympaki study area for two scenarios based on the length of the time-series, namely a 10-year period and a 36-year period. The S – O algorithm is developed and will be applied to enable the decision support system (DSS). More specifically, the algorithm refers to the optimum environmental management in terms of groundwater quantity.

In parallel, a schematic conceptualization of the fuzzy optimization procedure is given. The algorithm is under development and the results will be presented in a next version of the milestone or they will be incorporated into the deliverable of the current task.

1. Environmental criteria

1.1. Groundwater quantity

The simulation – optimization procedure consists of 3 components/sub-routines:

1. The groundwater modelling
2. The construction of a response matrix based on iterative simulation runs of the groundwater model.
3. The optimization of the pumping rates by using the response matrix.

1.1.1. Groundwater modelling with FEFLOW

The study area has a width of about 12.5 km and a length of about 9.1 km. There are 371 pumping wells which were grouped into 20 by using the K-nearest neighbors and each group was represented as one pumping well by using the Median Center method, which Identifies the location that minimizes overall Euclidean distance to the features in a dataset (Figure 11). The pumping rate of each group is the total pumping rate of all the wells constituting the group in m³/d. The pumping rates are imported in FEFLOW as timeseries with the values being different for the wet and dry season.

Figure 1: Tympaki study site with all the wells along with the representative ones for each group

The discretization of the unconfined aquifer was applied using a triangular finite element mesh which consists of 11,877 nodes and 15,340 elements. There are 2 layers and each one of them has 7,670 elements and 3 slices with 3,959 nodes for each slice. The depth of the model comprises 130 m deep from the sea level for the unconfined aquifer. The data for the hydraulic conductivity were extracted from the Decentralized Administration of Crete and they were set for the axis $x'x$ and $y'y$. For $z'z$ the hydraulic conductivity was 10% of the value of $x'x$. The pumping wells as considered in the model are depicted in Figure 12.

Figure 2: Pumping wells as introduced in the FEFLOW model

The calibration – validation process was conducted as follows. In the area of Tympaki, there are 6 observation wells that are scattered in the study area, as shown in Figure 13. The hydraulic head data are used as timeseries and the period for each well is different. The timeseries period for the precipitation, observation wells and pumping wells are available for the years 2004-2014. For the precipitation, the data of 1 station is used. For the sake of computational time, a mean precipitation was used with a step of 10 days and the input timeseries is in units of m/d. The data from 04/2004 to 04/2009 is used for calibration and the rest of the period is used for validation. During the validation period, the field measurements in the observation wells were conducted in random dates so there are periods with no data available in the observation wells.

Figure 3: Observation wells with calibration – validation data available.

For the model of the Tympaki area, a first-type flow boundary condition was used along the coastline, where the hydraulic head was set at 0 m. Also, a second-type boundary conditions were set at the north boundaries of the study area. Those boundary conditions are connected to the precipitation so there is a fluctuation to the hydraulic head that is relative to the rainfall. The observation wells that are used in the pumping scenarios were set to monitor the saltwater intrusion zone. As it appears in Figure 14, the intrusion zone is calculated at 5.65 meters above the sea level (at the end of the calibration period), by using the Ghyben – Herzberg relation and considering the depth of the deepest pumping well in the area (226 m from the sea level). The simulation runs are applied for a ten-year period from 01/04/2010 until 31/03/2020, by using the available precipitation data, as well as timeseries for the pumping rates. For the values of pumping rates obtained from the licences of water use, the results of the model are depicted in Figures 15 and 16 and the values of the hydraulic heads in the observation wells in Figure 17.

Figure 4: Saltwater intrusion zone at the end of calibration period

Figure 5: Current situation at the end of the wet period of the 10-year simulation

Figure 6: Current situation at the end of the dry period of the 10-year simulation

Figure 7: Hydraulic heads in the observation wells according to the current situation

1.1.2. Creation of the Response Matrix

The response matrix is created by sequentially disturbing the initial pumping rates of the m pumping wells, then running the simulation model and obtaining the hydraulic heads in n observation wells. The response matrix A is the $n \times m$ matrix, with its elements consisting of the values of hydraulic head's response to the disturbance of the pumping rate: $\frac{\partial H}{\partial Q}$.

In order to overcome the difficulties of the time-demanding runs of the groundwater simulation model, the response matrices can be constructed by using the results of the hydraulic heads and pumping rate values retrieved from a corresponding surrogate model. The ANN groundwater model that is being developed in WP3 of the project will be taken into consideration for integration into the simulation – optimization procedure. This way, the procedure can be fully automated, with no dependencies on the manual handling of a mainstream computational groundwater model.

1.1.3. Optimization of Pumping Rates

The optimization problem is set as:

$$\max Q$$

$$s. t. : H \geq H_{ref}$$

Where: $H = H_o + \partial H$ and $\partial H = A * \partial Q$

Therefore, the constraint:

$$H_o + \partial H \geq H_{ref} \rightarrow$$

$$H_o + A * \partial Q \geq H_{ref} \rightarrow$$

$$H_o + A * (Q - Q_o) \geq H_{ref} \rightarrow$$

$$A * Q \geq H_{ref} - H_o + A * Q_o$$

The problem is transformed to be in line with the requirements of Matlab optimization tool as:

$$\min(-Q)$$

$$s. t. : -A * Q \leq H_o - H_{ref} - A * Q_o$$

$-A$, the constraint coefficients matrix and

$b = H_o - H_{ref} - A * Q_o$, the vector of constraints of the linear problem.

Although the problem is not linear, it is solved by using the Simplex method in the frame of the piece-wise linear technique. Thus, after the first simulation – optimization cycle, the results for the optimum pumping rates are used in order to run again the simulation procedure, create the response matrix and apply the optimization procedure. The cycle is repeated until the results of two consecutive cycles converge to the same values for the individual wells and the total pumping rates as well. The results of the Tympaki study area are presented in the next section.

1.2. Results of the Simulation – Optimization Algorithm for the 10-year simulation period

At first, the simulation model was run for zero pumping rates. The saltwater intrusion zone is depicted in Figures 18 and 19, while the hydraulic heads in the observation wells in Figure 20. Then, the disturbance was set to 800 m³/day for one well at a time and the model was run separately for each disturbance in the corresponding pumping well. The results of the model for the hydraulic heads in the observation wells are in the 350th simulation step for the end of the dry period and in the 365th simulation step for the wet one. These results are recorded in Tables 1 and 2 for each simulation run and respective disturbance in the pumping wells. In this set of runs, the first response matrix A was retrieved as follows in Table 3 for the Dry Season and in Table 4 for the Wet Season.

Figure 8: Saltwater intrusion zone at the end of the dry period considering zero pumping rates

Figure 9: Saltwater intrusion zone at the end of the wet period considering zero pumping rates

Figure 10: Hydraulic head in the observation wells considering zero pumping rates

Table 1: Results of the simulation model – Hydraulic heads in observation wells at the end of the dry season when considering zero pumping rates

Simulation Run	Hydraulic Head in Observation well										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
R0	8.062363	8.515735	8.09704	8.500163	8.246379	8.492439	8.136183	8.490928	8.247511	8.327616	8.392923
R1	8.028379	8.470545	8.063345	8.45532	8.215493	8.448152	8.100444	8.447421	8.210038	8.287694	8.351131
R2	8.025531	8.476084	8.059861	8.460445	8.203752	8.450493	8.096794	8.447096	8.20567	8.281288	8.346124
R3	8.034139	8.459457	8.069227	8.444508	8.227885	8.43866	8.105735	8.44021	8.215087	8.289915	8.349379
R4	8.050494	8.507137	8.084746	8.4917	8.231376	8.482782	8.122806	8.480166	8.232749	8.311556	8.379094
R5	8.029436	8.466444	8.064596	8.451501	8.221748	8.44482	8.101194	8.444665	8.210867	8.287461	8.349762
R6	8.048526	8.453117	8.082819	8.442191	8.230791	8.447671	8.121219	8.454485	8.231178	8.307245	8.3669
R7	8.026039	8.471146	8.061229	8.455801	8.217177	8.448094	8.098081	8.446973	8.20811	8.286104	8.35007
R8	8.037851	8.509672	8.072611	8.49435	8.225151	8.48591	8.116352	8.483896	8.230663	8.316098	8.384129
R9	8.034556	8.455279	8.069661	8.44194	8.22469	8.438912	8.106259	8.441619	8.215785	8.291066	8.351004
R10	8.008265	8.484565	8.042866	8.469055	8.192627	8.4596	8.082998	8.456449	8.195878	8.283065	8.354017
R11	7.98478	8.497638	8.014678	8.481674	8.162338	8.472528	8.06684	8.469537	8.195908	8.293935	8.366803
R12	8.035878	8.498156	8.070279	8.482597	8.218075	8.472811	8.105415	8.469048	8.212077	8.288769	8.363705
R13	8.026825	8.471462	8.061786	8.456063	8.212435	8.448546	8.098983	8.447556	8.209042	8.287046	8.350911
R14	8.024205	8.472842	8.058551	8.457806	8.214351	8.449282	8.09624	8.447444	8.206124	8.284437	8.349258
R15	8.045973	8.480261	8.081069	8.462491	8.228095	8.448141	8.117967	8.442773	8.227444	8.301043	8.356462
R16	8.042262	8.506376	8.076554	8.491107	8.234863	8.48227	8.114219	8.479866	8.225028	8.308772	8.378465
R17	8.049289	8.512084	8.084343	8.496338	8.232813	8.488302	8.124327	8.486537	8.237051	8.320172	8.38725
R18	8.054364	8.481212	8.089056	8.468851	8.24757	8.467113	8.12756	8.469849	8.23803	8.315737	8.37769
R19	8.017876	8.477733	8.052768	8.461985	8.199913	8.453336	8.091242	8.451046	8.202478	8.284152	8.351302
R20	8.049884	8.501994	8.084652	8.486351	8.241845	8.476638	8.122024	8.473316	8.231538	8.307011	8.371512

Table 2: Results of the simulation model – Hydraulic heads in observation wells at the end of the wet season when considering zero pumping rates

Simulation Run	Hydraulic Head in Observation well										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
R0	14.949	15.18338	14.81602	15.11287	15.03934	15.13988	14.78852	15.10108	14.85455	14.87993	14.94165
R1	14.91422	15.13834	14.78079	15.06821	14.99795	15.09553	14.75209	15.05722	14.81706	14.83994	14.89983
R2	14.91237	15.14419	14.77946	15.07277	15.004	15.09795	14.74903	15.05718	14.81273	14.83363	14.89485
R3	14.92063	15.12714	14.78701	15.05722	14.9978	15.0861	14.75808	15.05014	14.82211	14.8422	14.8981
R4	14.93728	15.17524	14.80446	15.10404	15.02874	15.13024	14.77499	15.09023	14.83981	14.86389	14.92781
R5	14.91597	15.13415	14.78233	15.0642	14.9945	15.09226	14.75359	15.05461	14.8179	14.83975	14.89849
R6	14.93528	15.12143	14.80254	15.05468	15.02546	15.09511	14.77336	15.06454	14.83823	14.85958	14.91562
R7	14.91259	15.1387	14.779	15.06842	14.99244	15.09554	14.75051	15.05693	14.81514	14.8384	14.8988
R8	14.92459	15.17762	14.79226	15.10662	15.01751	15.13337	14.76847	15.09394	14.83771	14.86843	14.93285
R9	14.92113	15.123	14.78752	15.05461	15.00204	15.08635	14.7587	15.05159	14.82282	14.84337	14.89973
R10	14.89498	15.15281	14.76242	15.0815	14.98311	15.10705	14.73511	15.06648	14.80293	14.83539	14.90274
R11	14.87139	15.16506	14.73292	15.09426	14.93769	15.11997	14.71957	15.07952	14.80293	14.84624	14.91553
R12	14.92258	15.16659	14.7892	15.09503	15.00917	15.12026	14.7572	15.07907	14.81912	14.84108	14.91243
R13	14.9134	15.13881	14.78004	15.06871	14.99904	15.09599	14.75137	15.05754	14.81609	14.83938	14.89963
R14	14.91089	15.14127	14.77811	15.07017	14.99135	15.09673	14.7485	15.05746	14.81317	14.83675	14.89798
R15	14.9326	15.14766	14.79898	15.0752	15.02237	15.09559	14.77031	15.053	14.83449	14.85334	14.90517
R16	14.92894	15.17472	14.79591	15.10343	15.00827	15.12974	14.76636	15.08968	14.83207	14.86109	14.9272
R17	14.93591	15.17957	14.80268	15.10907	15.02832	15.13574	14.77676	15.09643	14.84409	14.87249	14.93598
R18	14.94105	15.14948	14.80796	15.08117	15.02112	15.11454	14.77968	15.07992	14.84507	14.86805	14.92642
R19	14.9045	15.1453	14.7715	15.07471	14.99448	15.10079	14.74365	15.06109	14.80952	14.83647	14.90002
R20	14.93656	15.17018	14.80324	15.09868	15.01677	15.12408	14.7742	15.0832	14.83858	14.85933	14.92024

Table 3: Response matrix for the dry season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-42.48	-46.04	-35.28	-14.84	-41.16	-17.30	-45.40	-30.64	-34.76	-67.62	-96.98	-33.11	-44.42	-47.70	-20.49	-25.13	-16.34	-10.00	-55.61	-15.60
-56.49	-49.56	-70.35	-10.75	-61.61	-78.27	-55.74	-7.58	-75.57	-38.96	-22.62	-21.97	-55.34	-53.62	-44.34	-11.70	-4.56	-43.15	-47.50	-17.18
-42.12	-46.47	-34.77	-15.37	-40.55	-17.78	-44.76	-30.54	-34.22	-67.72	-102.95	-33.45	-44.07	-48.11	-19.96	-25.61	-15.87	-9.98	-55.34	-15.48
-56.05	-49.65	-69.57	-10.58	-60.83	-72.47	-55.45	-7.27	-72.78	-38.88	-23.11	-21.96	-55.13	-52.95	-47.09	-11.32	-4.78	-39.14	-47.72	-17.26
-38.61	-53.28	-23.12	-18.75	-30.79	-19.48	-36.50	-26.53	-27.11	-67.19	-105.05	-35.38	-42.43	-40.03	-22.85	-14.39	-16.96	1.49	-58.08	-5.67
-55.36	-52.43	-67.22	-12.07	-59.52	-55.96	-55.43	-8.16	-66.91	-41.05	-24.89	-24.53	-54.87	-53.95	-55.37	-12.71	-5.17	-31.66	-48.88	-19.75
-44.67	-49.24	-38.06	-16.72	-43.74	-18.71	-47.63	-24.79	-37.41	-66.48	-86.68	-38.46	-46.50	-49.93	-22.77	-27.46	-14.82	-10.78	-56.18	-17.70
-54.38	-54.79	-63.40	-13.45	-57.83	-45.55	-54.94	-8.79	-61.64	-43.10	-26.74	-27.35	-54.21	-54.35	-60.19	-13.83	-5.49	-26.35	-49.85	-22.01
-46.84	-52.30	-40.53	-18.45	-45.80	-20.42	-49.25	-21.06	-39.66	-64.54	-64.50	-44.29	-48.09	-51.73	-25.08	-28.10	-13.08	-11.85	-56.29	-19.97
-49.90	-57.91	-47.13	-20.08	-50.19	-25.46	-51.89	-14.40	-45.69	-55.69	-42.10	-48.56	-50.71	-53.97	-33.22	-23.56	-9.31	-14.85	-54.33	-25.76
-52.24	-58.50	-54.43	-17.29	-53.95	-32.53	-53.57	-10.99	-52.40	-48.63	-32.65	-36.52	-52.51	-54.58	-45.58	-18.07	-7.09	-19.04	-52.03	-26.76

Table 4: Response matrix for the wet season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-43.47	-45.79	-35.46	-14.65	-41.29	-17.15	-45.51	-30.51	-34.84	-67.52	-97.01	-33.02	-44.50	-47.64	-20.50	-25.07	-16.36	-9.94	-55.62	-15.55
-56.30	-48.99	-70.30	-10.17	-61.54	-77.44	-55.85	-7.20	-75.48	-38.21	-22.90	-20.99	-55.71	-52.64	-44.65	-10.82	-4.76	-42.37	-47.60	-16.50
-44.04	-45.70	-36.26	-14.45	-42.11	-16.85	-46.28	-29.70	-35.62	-67.00	-103.88	-33.53	-44.98	-47.39	-21.30	-25.14	-16.67	-10.08	-55.65	-15.97
-55.82	-50.12	-69.56	-11.04	-60.84	-72.74	-55.56	-7.81	-72.82	-39.21	-23.26	-22.30	-55.20	-53.38	-47.09	-11.80	-4.75	-39.62	-47.70	-17.74
-51.74	-44.17	-51.92	-13.25	-56.05	-17.35	-58.62	-27.29	-46.63	-70.29	-127.06	-37.71	-50.37	-59.99	-21.21	-38.84	-13.77	-22.77	-56.07	-28.21
-55.44	-52.41	-67.22	-12.05	-59.53	-55.96	-55.43	-8.14	-66.91	-41.04	-24.89	-24.52	-54.86	-53.94	-55.36	-12.67	-5.17	-31.67	-48.86	-19.75
-45.54	-49.36	-38.05	-16.91	-43.66	-18.95	-47.51	-25.06	-37.28	-66.76	-86.19	-39.15	-46.44	-50.03	-22.76	-27.70	-14.70	-11.05	-56.09	-17.90
-54.83	-54.87	-63.67	-13.56	-58.09	-45.68	-55.19	-8.92	-61.86	-43.25	-26.95	-27.51	-54.43	-54.52	-60.10	-14.25	-5.81	-26.45	-49.99	-22.35
-46.86	-52.27	-40.55	-18.42	-45.81	-20.40	-49.26	-21.05	-39.66	-64.52	-64.52	-44.29	-48.07	-51.73	-25.07	-28.10	-13.08	-11.85	-56.29	-19.96
-49.99	-57.88	-47.16	-20.05	-50.22	-25.44	-51.91	-14.37	-45.70	-55.67	-42.11	-48.56	-50.69	-53.97	-33.24	-23.55	-9.30	-14.85	-54.32	-25.75
-52.27	-58.50	-54.44	-17.30	-53.95	-32.54	-53.56	-11.00	-52.40	-48.64	-32.65	-36.52	-52.52	-54.59	-45.60	-18.06	-7.09	-19.04	-52.04	-26.76

The optimum pumping rates were determined for four different values for the water table level of reference, H_{ref} : a) $H_{ref}=6,25$ m (upgrading water level up to 0,60 m), b) $H_{ref}=6,5$ m (upgrading water level up to 0,85 m), c) $H_{ref}=6,75$ m (upgrading water level up to 1,1 m) and d) $H_{ref}=7$ m (upgrading water level up to 1,35 m). The water table level in the observation wells is constrained to values greater than H_{ref} . Additionally, the lower bounds of the pumping rates were set to zero and the upper bounds were determined by the licenses held.

1.2.1. Optimum Pumping Rates for $H_{ref} = 6.25$ m

The optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.25$ m were found after 2 iterations of the procedure. The first optimization run was based on the first response matrix (Tables 3 and 4). The calculated b vector for the constraints' values was found as recorded in Table 5.

Table 5: b vector of constraints for the first run of $H_{ref} = 6.25$ m

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.8124	1	8.699
2	2.2657	2	8.9334
3	1.8470	3	8.5660
4	2.2502	4	8.8629
5	1.9964	5	8.7893
6	2.2424	6	8.8899
7	1.8862	7	8.5385
8	2.2409	8	8.8511
9	1.9975	9	8.6046
10	2.0776	10	8.6299
11	2.1429	11	8.6917

The optimum values of the pumping rates were found as shown in Table 6 for the wet and the dry season.

Table 6: Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the first run of $H_{ref} = 6.25m$

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.164
2	8,698.63	8,698.63
3	10,257.63	8,687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3,474.58	3,420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.82
8	474.19	381.20
9	1,497.99	815.75
10	1,334.78	1,295.06
11	1,559.42	1,559.42
12	1,099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2,955.60	2,410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.11	140.08
19	1,561.13	267.90
20	162.72	92.96
Total pumping rate	$3.7486 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$

For the second simulation – optimization procedure the optimum values found in the previous set were used as the initial ones. The model was run for the initial pumping rates as well as for the disturbed ones. For this set of runs, the disturbance was set to 10% of the initial pumping rates. The same procedure as in the previous step was followed and the results for the optimum pumping rates are recorded in Table 7. The second response matrix A and the calculated b vector are available in the Appendix.

Table 7: Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the second run of $H_{ref} = 6.25\text{m}$

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.164
2	8,698.63	8,698.63
3	10,257.63	8,687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3,474.58	3,420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.82
8	474.19	381.20
9	1,497.99	815.75
10	1,334.78	1,295.06
11	1,559.42	1,559.42
12	1,099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2,955.60	2,410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.11	140.08
19	1,561.13	267.90
20	162.72	92.96
Total pumping rate	$3.7486 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$

The values obtained from the second iteration are the same with these of the first one. Therefore, these pumping rates are the optimum ones for upgrading the water table level up to 0.60 m and for the dry season are graphically presented in Figure 21. The saltwater intrusion zone is shown in Figures 22 and 23 and the water level in the observation wells in Figure 24.

Figure 11: Optimum pumping rates for the dry season

Figure 12: Saltwater intrusion at the end of the dry season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.25m$

Figure 13: Saltwater intrusion at the end of the wet season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.25\text{m}$

Figure 14: Hydraulic heads in the observation wells considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.25\text{m}$

1.2.2. Optimum Pumping Rates for $H_{ref} = 6.5$ m

The optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref}=6,5m$ were found after 3 iterations of the procedure. The first optimization run was based on the first response matrix (Tables 3 and 4). The calculated b vector for the constraints' values was found as shown in Table 8.

Table 8: b vector of constraints for the first run of $H_{ref} = 6.5m$

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.562363	1	8.449
2	2.015735	2	8.68338
3	1.59704	3	8.31602
4	2.000163	4	8.61287
5	1.746379	5	8.53934
6	1.992439	6	8.63988
7	1.636183	7	8.28852
8	1.990928	8	8.60108
9	1.747511	9	8.35455
10	1.827616	10	8.37993
11	1.892923	11	8.44165

The optimum values of the pumping rates were found as shown in Table 9 for the wet and the dry season.

Table 9: Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the first run of $H_{ref} = 6.5m$

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.16
2	8,698.63	8,698.63
3	10,257.63	8,687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3,474.58	3,420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.81
8	474.19	381.20
9	1,371.23	815.75
10	1,334.78	1,295.06
11	1,280.68	1,559.42
12	1,099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2,955.60	2,410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	1,561.13	267.90
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	$3.7080 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$

For the second simulation – optimization procedure the optimum values found in the previous set were used as the initial ones. The model was run for the initial pumping rates as well as for the disturbed ones. For this set of runs, the disturbance was set to 10% of the initial pumping rate. The same procedure as in the previous step was followed and the results for the optimum pumping rates are recorded in Table 10. The simulation results, the second response matrix A and the calculated b vector are available in the Appendix.

Table 10: Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the second run of $H_{ref} = 6.5m$

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.16
2	8,698.63	8,698.63
3	10,257.63	8,687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3,474.58	3,420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.81
8	474.19	381.20
9	1,498.00	815.75
10	1,334.78	1,295.06
11	1,472.43	1,559.42
12	1,099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2,955.60	2,410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	1,561.13	267.90
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	$3.7399 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$

Concerning the wet season, the optimum values from the two consecutive runs are the same. However, for the dry season, there are two pumping wells that their pumping rates have a difference in their values, as shown in Figure 25. Therefore, the same procedure is repeated for a third time and optimum pumping rates are recorded in Table 11. For the third set of runs, the disturbance was set to 20% of the initial pumping rate. The simulation results, the third response matrix A and the calculated b vector are available in the Appendix. The optimum values of the third iteration converge with these from the second one, as depicted in Figure 26. Therefore, the problem has been linearized and the final optimum values are those of the third iteration.

Table 11: Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the third run of Href = 6.5m

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.16
2	8,698.63	8,698.63
3	10,257.63	8,687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3,474.58	3,420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.81
8	474.19	381.20
9	1,498.00	815.75
10	1,334.78	1,295.06
11	1,464.07	1,559.42
12	1,099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2,955.60	2,410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	1,561.13	267.90
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7390·10 ⁴	3.1254·10 ⁴

Figure 15: Optimum Pumping Rates for the Dry Season form the first and second S-O runs for $H_{ref} = 6.5m$

Figure 16: Optimum Pumping Rates for the Dry Season form the first, second and third S-O runs for $H_{ref} = 6.5m$

The hydraulic head level in the observation wells is shown in the following Figure 29 and the saltwater intrusion front at the end of the dry and the wet period of the 10-year simulation in Figures 27 and 28.

Figure 17: Saltwater intrusion at the end of the dry season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.5\text{m}$

Figure 18: Saltwater intrusion at the end of the wet season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.5\text{m}$

Figure 19: Hydraulic heads in observation wells when considering optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.5\text{m}$

1.2.3. Optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.75$ m

The simulation – optimization runs that were executed aiming at upgrading the water table level up to 1.1 m followed the pattern summarized in Table 12.

1.2.4. Optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 7$ m

The simulation – optimization runs that were executed aiming at upgrading the water table level up to 1.35 m followed the pattern summarized in Table 13.

Table 12: Description of the simulation – optimization run parameters and results for $H_{ref} = 6.75m$

Run	Initial Pumping Rates	Disturbances		Optimum Values for Pumping Rates	Number of Wells in which there is convergence with previous run's results	Total Pumping Rates (m ³ /day)	
		If $Q_0 = 0$	If $Q_0 \neq 0$			Dry Season	Wet Season
1	0	800	0.1 of Q_0	Qopt1	-	$3.2451 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
2	Qopt1	800	0.1 of Q_0	Qopt2	13	$3.7331 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
3	Qopt2	800	0.2 of Q_0	Qopt3	14	$3.7357 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
4	Qopt3	800	0.3 of Q_0	Qopt4	13	$3.2931 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
5	Qopt4	800	0.4 of Q_0	Qopt5	13	$3.2860 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
6	Qopt5	800	0.5 of Q_0	Qopt6	12	$3.3457 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
7	Qopt6	800	0.6 of Q_0	Qopt7	14	$3.3008 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
8	Qopt7	800	0.7 of Q_0	Qopt8	18	$3.7486 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
9a	Qopt8	800	0.8 of Q_0	Qopt9a	14	$3.2886 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
9b	Qopt8	800	0.1 of Q_0	Qopt9b	17	$3.2881 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
11	Qopt9b	800	0.2 of Q_0	Qopt11	13	$3.3189 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$

Table 13: Description of the simulation – optimization run parameters and results for $H_{ref} = 7$ m

Run	Initial Pumping Rates	Disturbances		Optimum Values for Pumping Rates	Number of Wells in which there is convergence with previous run's results	Total Pumping Rates (m ³ /day)	
		If $Q_0 = 0$	If $Q_0 \neq 0$			Dry Season	Wet Season
1	0	800	0.1 of Q_0	Qopt1	-	$2.7644 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
2	Qopt1	800	0.1 of Q_0	Qopt2	11	$2.8303 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
3	Qopt2	800	0.2 of Q_0	Qopt3	12	$3.5512 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
4	Qopt3	800	0.3 of Q_0	Qopt4	13	$2.7824 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
5	Qopt4	800	0.4 of Q_0	Qopt5	15	$2.8229 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
6a	Qopt5	800	0.5 of Q_0	Qopt6a	12	$2.8425 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$
6b	Qopt5	800	0.1 of Q_0	Qopt6b	13	$3.3961 \cdot 10^4$	$3.1254 \cdot 10^4$

1.3. Results of the Simulation – Optimization Algorithm for the 36-year simulation period

At first, the simulation model was run for zero pumping rates. The saltwater intrusion zone is depicted in Figures 20 and 21, while the hydraulic heads in the observation wells in Figure 22. Then, the disturbance was set to 800 m³/day for one well at a time and the model was run separately for each disturbance in the corresponding pumping well. The results of the model for the hydraulic heads in the observation wells are in the 1,292nd simulation step for the end of the dry period and in the 1,312th simulation step for the wet one. These results are recorded in Tables 14 and 15 for each simulation run and respective disturbance in the pumping wells. In this set of runs, the first response matrix A was retrieved as follows in Table 16 for the Dry Season and in Table 17 for the Wet Season.

Figure 20: Saltwater intrusion zone at the end of the dry period considering zero pumping rates

Figure 21: Saltwater intrusion zone at the end of the wet period considering zero pumping rates

Figure 22: Hydraulic head in the observation wells considering zero pumping rates

Table 14: Results of the simulation model – Hydraulic heads in observation wells at the end of the dry season when considering zero pumping rates

Simulation Run	Hydraulic Head in Observation well										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
R0	6.50575	6.810789	6.481448	6.789786	6.652736	6.821875	6.566662	6.827519	6.661407	6.741845	6.777572
R1	6.471607	6.765771	6.447102	6.745069	6.616716	6.777672	6.530708	6.783928	6.62403	6.702003	6.735879
R2	6.468923	6.771359	6.444509	6.749902	6.613608	6.779911	6.527208	6.783623	6.619557	6.695506	6.730751
R3	6.477494	6.754532	6.453019	6.734112	6.622599	6.768099	6.536232	6.776684	6.628981	6.704138	6.734034
R4	6.493939	6.802421	6.469481	6.781115	6.639825	6.812222	6.553217	6.816702	6.64665	6.725795	6.763741
R5	6.472778	6.76153	6.44835	6.741112	6.617868	6.774253	6.531711	6.781143	6.624758	6.70168	6.734414
R6	6.49197	6.748525	6.467561	6.731714	6.637894	6.777104	6.551609	6.791017	6.645079	6.721483	6.751548
R7	6.469388	6.766019	6.444999	6.745375	6.614555	6.777535	6.528615	6.783457	6.622003	6.700326	6.734722
R8	6.481286	6.805097	6.457321	6.783715	6.631098	6.815353	6.54673	6.82042	6.644563	6.730334	6.768778
R9	6.477913	6.750211	6.453473	6.731617	6.623114	6.768347	6.536801	6.778109	6.629678	6.705289	6.735656
R10	6.451693	6.780029	6.427528	6.758478	6.597635	6.789039	6.513373	6.792968	6.609777	6.697299	6.738666
R11	6.428161	6.792516	6.398602	6.77129	6.56254	6.801964	6.497488	6.806032	6.609793	6.70816	6.751454
R12	6.479297	6.793642	6.454652	6.772042	6.617384	6.80225	6.535654	6.805564	6.625974	6.703	6.748355
R13	6.470181	6.766349	6.445991	6.745683	6.621087	6.777982	6.529506	6.784053	6.622944	6.701281	6.735561
R14	6.467612	6.768299	6.442921	6.747238	6.608685	6.77872	6.526726	6.783957	6.620024	6.698665	6.733907
R15	6.489364	6.775188	6.465187	6.752125	6.637496	6.777585	6.548408	6.779379	6.64134	6.715265	6.7411
R16	6.485662	6.801787	6.460895	6.780529	6.629782	6.811713	6.544665	6.816248	6.638927	6.723004	6.763123
R17	6.492674	6.807057	6.468561	6.785975	6.641247	6.817734	6.554821	6.823059	6.650944	6.734405	6.771903
R18	6.49777	6.776581	6.473277	6.758276	6.643549	6.796538	6.557975	6.806343	6.651928	6.729961	6.762342
R19	6.461259	6.772747	6.4371	6.751616	6.60728	6.782782	6.521742	6.7876	6.616373	6.698385	6.735951
R20	6.493289	6.797319	6.468777	6.775782	6.63887	6.806074	6.552451	6.809747	6.645435	6.72124	6.756164

Table 15: Results of the simulation model – Hydraulic heads in observation wells at the end of the wet season when considering zero pumping rates

Simulation Run	Hydraulic Head in Observation well										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
R0	6.875884	7.214381	6.850089	7.191123	7.029808	7.221935	6.939067	7.22503	7.038718	7.125317	7.166835
R1	6.841738	7.16936	6.81574	7.146404	6.993787	7.17773	6.90311	7.181436	7.001338	7.085472	7.125138
R2	6.839059	7.174952	6.813151	7.151239	6.990682	7.179973	6.899613	7.181135	6.996867	7.078978	7.120014
R3	6.847628	7.158123	6.82166	7.135448	6.999672	7.16816	6.908636	7.174195	7.006291	7.08761	7.123296
R4	6.864073	7.206013	6.838123	7.182487	7.016899	7.212283	6.925622	7.214214	7.023961	7.109268	7.153003
R5	6.842912	7.165122	6.816991	7.142449	6.994942	7.174314	6.904116	7.178654	7.002069	7.085152	7.123677
R6	6.862104	7.15212	6.836202	7.133052	7.014967	7.177164	6.924014	7.188528	7.022389	7.104955	7.14081
R7	6.839522	7.169607	6.81364	7.146711	6.991628	7.177595	6.90102	7.180968	6.999313	7.083798	7.123984
R8	6.85142	7.208688	6.825963	7.185051	7.008172	7.215413	6.919135	7.217931	7.021873	7.113806	7.15804
R9	6.848047	7.153804	6.822115	7.132954	7.000188	7.168408	6.909206	7.175621	7.006989	7.088762	7.124918
R10	6.821827	7.18362	6.79617	7.159815	6.974709	7.1891	6.885778	7.19048	6.987088	7.080771	7.127928
R11	6.798296	7.196109	6.767241	7.172627	6.93965	7.202024	6.869894	7.203543	6.987103	7.091633	7.140716
R12	6.849431	7.197234	6.823293	7.17338	6.99443	7.202311	6.908058	7.203075	7.003285	7.086473	7.137618
R13	6.840315	7.169941	6.814635	7.14702	6.998136	7.178043	6.90191	7.181565	7.000254	7.084753	7.124823
R14	6.837746	7.171891	6.811562	7.148575	6.985783	7.178781	6.899131	7.181468	6.997335	7.082137	7.123169
R15	6.859498	7.17878	6.833828	7.153462	7.014552	7.177646	6.920812	7.176892	7.01865	7.098737	7.130362
R16	6.855796	7.205379	6.829538	7.181866	7.006867	7.211773	6.91707	7.213757	7.016237	7.106476	7.152385
R17	6.862808	7.210649	6.837201	7.187312	7.018314	7.217794	6.927226	7.22057	7.028254	7.117877	7.161165
R18	6.867904	7.180173	6.841919	7.159613	7.020627	7.196599	6.93038	7.203855	7.029238	7.113433	7.151604
R19	6.831393	7.176339	6.805741	7.152953	6.984351	7.182843	6.894147	7.185111	6.993683	7.081857	7.125213
R20	6.863423	7.200911	6.837418	7.177118	7.015945	7.206134	6.924855	7.207259	7.022746	7.104712	7.145426

Table 16: Response matrix for the dry season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.27	-4.60	-3.53	-1.48	-4.12	-1.72	-4.55	-3.06	-3.48	-6.76	-9.70	-3.31	-4.45	-4.77	-2.05	-2.51	-1.63	-1.00	-5.56	-1.56
-5.63	-4.93	-7.03	-1.05	-6.16	-7.78	-5.60	-0.71	-7.57	-3.84	-2.28	-2.14	-5.55	-5.31	-4.45	-1.13	-0.47	-4.28	-4.76	-1.68
-4.29	-4.62	-3.55	-1.50	-4.14	-1.74	-4.56	-3.02	-3.50	-6.74	-10.36	-3.35	-4.43	-4.82	-2.03	-2.57	-1.61	-1.02	-5.54	-1.58
-5.59	-4.99	-6.96	-1.08	-6.08	-7.26	-5.55	-0.76	-7.27	-3.91	-2.31	-2.22	-5.51	-5.32	-4.71	-1.16	-0.48	-3.94	-4.77	-1.75
-4.50	-4.89	-3.77	-1.61	-4.36	-1.86	-4.77	-2.70	-3.70	-6.89	-11.27	-4.42	-3.96	-5.51	-1.91	-2.87	-1.44	-1.15	-5.68	-1.73
-5.53	-5.25	-6.72	-1.21	-5.95	-5.60	-5.54	-0.82	-6.69	-4.10	-2.49	-2.45	-5.49	-5.39	-5.54	-1.27	-0.52	-3.17	-4.89	-1.98
-4.49	-4.93	-3.80	-1.68	-4.37	-1.88	-4.76	-2.49	-3.73	-6.66	-8.65	-3.88	-4.64	-4.99	-2.28	-2.75	-1.48	-1.09	-5.62	-1.78
-5.45	-5.49	-6.35	-1.35	-5.80	-4.56	-5.51	-0.89	-6.18	-4.32	-2.69	-2.74	-5.43	-5.45	-6.02	-1.41	-0.56	-2.65	-4.99	-2.22
-4.67	-5.23	-4.05	-1.84	-4.58	-2.04	-4.93	-2.11	-3.97	-6.45	-6.45	-4.43	-4.81	-5.17	-2.51	-2.81	-1.31	-1.18	-5.63	-2.00
-4.98	-5.79	-4.71	-2.01	-5.02	-2.55	-5.19	-1.44	-4.57	-5.57	-4.21	-4.86	-5.07	-5.40	-3.32	-2.36	-0.93	-1.49	-5.43	-2.58
-5.21	-5.85	-5.44	-1.73	-5.39	-3.25	-5.36	-1.10	-5.24	-4.86	-3.26	-3.65	-5.25	-5.46	-4.56	-1.81	-0.71	-1.90	-5.20	-2.68

Table 17: Response matrix for the wet season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.27	-4.60	-3.53	-1.48	-4.12	-1.72	-4.55	-3.06	-3.48	-6.76	-9.70	-3.31	-4.45	-4.77	-2.05	-2.51	-1.63	-1.00	-5.56	-1.56
-5.63	-4.93	-7.03	-1.05	-6.16	-7.78	-5.60	-0.71	-7.57	-3.85	-2.28	-2.14	-5.56	-5.31	-4.45	-1.13	-0.47	-4.28	-4.76	-1.68
-4.29	-4.62	-3.55	-1.50	-4.14	-1.74	-4.56	-3.02	-3.50	-6.74	-10.36	-3.35	-4.43	-4.82	-2.03	-2.57	-1.61	-1.02	-5.54	-1.58
-5.59	-4.99	-6.96	-1.08	-6.08	-7.26	-5.55	-0.76	-7.27	-3.91	-2.31	-2.22	-5.51	-5.32	-4.71	-1.16	-0.48	-3.94	-4.77	-1.75
-4.50	-4.89	-3.77	-1.61	-4.36	-1.86	-4.77	-2.70	-3.70	-6.89	-11.27	-4.42	-3.96	-5.50	-1.91	-2.87	-1.44	-1.15	-5.68	-1.73
-5.53	-5.25	-6.72	-1.21	-5.95	-5.60	-5.54	-0.82	-6.69	-4.10	-2.49	-2.45	-5.49	-5.39	-5.54	-1.27	-0.52	-3.17	-4.89	-1.98
-4.49	-4.93	-3.80	-1.68	-4.37	-1.88	-4.76	-2.49	-3.73	-6.66	-8.65	-3.88	-4.64	-4.99	-2.28	-2.75	-1.48	-1.09	-5.61	-1.78
-5.45	-5.49	-6.35	-1.35	-5.80	-4.56	-5.51	-0.89	-6.18	-4.32	-2.69	-2.74	-5.43	-5.45	-6.02	-1.41	-0.56	-2.65	-4.99	-2.22
-4.67	-5.23	-4.05	-1.84	-4.58	-2.04	-4.93	-2.11	-3.97	-6.45	-6.45	-4.43	-4.81	-5.17	-2.51	-2.81	-1.31	-1.18	-5.63	-2.00
-4.98	-5.79	-4.71	-2.01	-5.02	-2.55	-5.19	-1.44	-4.57	-5.57	-4.21	-4.86	-5.07	-5.40	-3.32	-2.36	-0.93	-1.49	-5.43	-2.58
-5.21	-5.85	-5.44	-1.73	-5.39	-3.25	-5.36	-1.10	-5.24	-4.86	-3.26	-3.65	-5.25	-5.46	-4.56	-1.81	-0.71	-1.90	-5.20	-2.68

The optimum pumping rates were determined for two different values for the water table level of reference, H_{ref} : a) $H_{ref} = 6.25$ m (upgrading water level up to 0.60 m), b) $H_{ref} = 6.48$ m (upgrading water level up to 0.83 m). The water table level in the observation wells is constrained to values greater than H_{ref} . Additionally, the lower bounds of the pumping rates were set to zero and the upper bounds were determined by the licenses held.

1.3.1. Optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.25$ m

The optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.25$ m were found after 4 iterations of the procedure. The first optimization run was based on the first response matrix (Tables 16 and 17). The calculated b vector for the constraints' values was found as recorded in Table 18.

Table 18: b vector of constraints for the first run of $H_{ref} = 6.25$ m

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	0.25575	1	0.625884
2	0.560789	2	0.964381
3	0.231448	3	0.600089
4	0.539786	4	0.941123
5	0.402736	5	0.779808
6	0.571875	6	0.971935
7	0.316662	7	0.689067
8	0.577519	8	0.97503
9	0.411407	9	0.788718
10	0.491845	10	0.875317
11	0.527572	11	0.916835

The optimum values of the pumping rates were found as shown in Table 19 for the wet and the dry season, as well as in Figure 23.

Table 19: Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the first run of $H_{ref}=6.25m$

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	0.00	0,00
2	0.00	4,667.93
3	1,989.94	8,441.07
4	177.94	62.90
5	0.00	0.00
6	920.55	920.55
7	0.00	0.00
8	474.19	381.20
9	1,498.00	0.00
10	0.00	0.00
11	0.00	0.00
12	1,099.19	950.55
13	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.00
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	0.00	0.00
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	8,284.49	16,648.01

For the second simulation – optimization procedure the optimum values found in the previous set were used as the initial ones. The model was run for the initial pumping rates as well as for the disturbed ones. For this set of runs, the disturbance was set to 20% of the initial pumping rates. The same procedure as in the previous step was followed and the results for the optimum pumping rates are recorded in Table 20 and depicted in Figure 24. The second response matrix A and the calculated b vector are available in the Appendix 2.

Table 20: Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the second run of $H_{ref} = 6.25m$

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	5,452.43
3	6,206.54	8,514.71
4	177.94	62.90
5	0.00	0.00
6	920.55	920.55
7	0.00	0.00
8	0.00	381.20
9	0.00	0.00
10	0.00	0.00
11	0.00	0.00
12	0.00	950.55
13	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.00
15	0.00	349.11
16	0.00	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	0.00	0.00
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	8,385.64	17,506.15

Figure 23: Optimum Pumping Rates and Upper Bounds for the first run of $H_{ref} = 6.25m$

Figure 24: Optimum Pumping Rates and Upper Bounds for the second run of $H_{ref} = 6.25m$

For the third simulation – optimization procedure the optimum values found in the previous set were used as the initial ones. The model was run for the initial pumping rates as well as for the disturbed ones. For this set of runs, the disturbance was set to 30% of the initial pumping rates. The same procedure as in the previous step was followed and the results for the optimum pumping rates are recorded in Table 21 and graphically shown in Figure 25. The third response matrix A and the calculated b vector are available in the Appendix 2.

Table 21: Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the second run of $H_{ref} = 6.25m$

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	5,288.33
3	3,647.35	8,687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	0.00	0.00
6	920.55	803.42
7	0.00	0.00
8	0.00	381.20
9	0.00	0.00
10	0.00	0.00
11	0.00	0.00
12	0.00	950.55
13	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.00
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	0.00	0.00
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	6,870.51	17,397.76

For the fourth and final simulation – optimization procedure the optimum values found in the previous set were used as the initial ones. The model was run for the initial pumping rates as well as for the disturbed ones. For this set of runs, the disturbance was set to 40% of the initial pumping rates. The same procedure as in the previous step was followed and the results for the optimum pumping rates are recorded in Table 22 and graphically shown in Figure 26. The status of the study area when applying the optimum pumping rates is presented in Figures 27 and 28 for the wet and dry season respectively. The final response matrix A and the calculated b vector are available in the Appendix 2.

Table 22: Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the second run of $H_{ref} = 6.25m$

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	5,532.70
3	4,116.89	8,534.78
4	177.94	62.90
5	0.00	0.00
6	920.55	920.55
7	0.00	0.00
8	0.00	381.20
9	0.00	0.00
10	0.00	0.00
11	0.00	0.00
12	0.00	950.55
13	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.00
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	0.00	0.00
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	7,340.05	17,606.50

Figure 25: Optimum Pumping Rates and Upper Bounds for the third run of $H_{ref} = 6.25m$

Figure 26: Optimum Pumping Rates and Upper Bounds for the fourth run of $H_{ref} = 6.25m$

Figure 27: Saltwater intrusion at the end of the wet season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.25\text{m}$

Figure 28: Saltwater intrusion at the end of the dry season considering the optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.25\text{m}$

1.3.2. Optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.48$ m

The optimum pumping rates for $H_{ref} = 6.48$ m were found after 2 iterations of the procedure. The first optimization run was based on the first response matrix (Tables 16 and 17). The calculated b vector for the constraints' values was found as recorded in Table 23.

Table 23: b vector of constraints for the first run of $H_{ref} = 6.48$ m

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	0.02575	1	0.395884
2	0.330789	2	0.734381
3	0.001448	3	0.370089
4	0.309786	4	0.711123
5	0.172736	5	0.549808
6	0.341875	6	0.741935
7	0.086662	7	0.459067
8	0.347519	8	0.74503
9	0.181407	9	0.558718
10	0.261845	10	0.645317
11	0.297572	11	0.686835

The optimum values of the pumping rates were found as shown in Table 24 for the wet and the dry season and represented in Figure 29. The saltwater intrusion front is presented in Figures 30 and 31.

Table 24: Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the first run of $H_{ref} = 6.48$ m

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	0.00
3	0.00	7,231.18
4	0.00	62.90
5	0.00	0.00
6	0.00	920.55
7	0.00	0.00
8	0.00	381.20
9	0.00	815.75
10	0.00	0.00
11	0.00	0.00
12	0.00	950.55
13	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.00
15	0.00	349.11
16	0.00	417.99
17	0.00	223.67
18	141.77	140.08
19	0.00	0.00
20	0.00	92.96
Total pumping rate	141.77	11,585.95

Figure 29: Optimum Pumping Rates and Upper Bounds for the first run of $H_{ref} = 6.48$ m

Figure 30: Saltwater intrusion at the end of the wet season considering the optimum pumping rates of the first run for $H_{ref} = 6.48$ m

Figure 31: Saltwater intrusion at the end of the dry season considering the optimum pumping rates of the first run for $H_{ref} = 6.48$ m

For the second simulation – optimization procedure the optimum values found in the previous set were used as the initial ones. The model was run for the initial pumping rates as well as for the disturbed ones. For this set of runs, the disturbance was set to 20% of the initial pumping rates. The same procedure as in the previous step was followed and the results for the optimum pumping rates are recorded in Table 25 and graphically represented in Figure 32. The linear programming optimization was not feasible for the dry season (Figure 33). The second response matrix A and the calculated b vector are available in the Appendix 2.

Table 25: Optimum Pumping Rates per Season for the second run of $H_{ref} = 6.48$ m

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	-	0.00
2	-	201.28
3	-	8,109.21
4	-	62.90
5	-	0.00
6	-	920.55
7	-	0.00
8	-	381.20

9	-	815.75
10	-	0.00
11	-	0.00
12	-	950.55
13	-	0.00
14	-	0.00
15	-	349.11
16	-	417.99
17	-	223.67
18	-	140.08
19	-	0.00
20	-	92.96
Total pumping rate	-	12,665.26

Figure 32: Optimum Pumping Rates and Upper Bounds for the second run of $H_{ref} = 6.48\text{m}$ for the wet season

```

Command Window

Href =

    6.4800

No feasible solution found.

Linprog stopped because no point satisfies the constraints.

Qopt_DrySeason =

     []

val_dry =

     []

```

Figure 33: Outcome of the linear programming optimization for the second run of $H_{ref} = 6.48$ m for the dry season

1.4. Discussion

The piece-wise linear technique was applied for four different values of the hydraulic head of reference (scenarios) and for the same 10-year period of simulation. with precipitation data available. As observed from the different scenarios, the higher the hydraulic head of reference, the more difficult to obtain the optimum values of the pumping rates. For the two first scenarios, the optimum values were found after two and three iterations, respectively. On the other hand, in the third and fourth scenarios, an optimal solution could not be found at all. In these scenarios, it was also observed that after a certain number of iterations, a maximum number of wells in which there is convergence between two consecutive runs exists, but does not reach the total number of the pumping wells. Therefore, it is assumed that the constraint is strict enough so as not to enable the finding of the optimum solution for the certain duration of the simulation period.

For the 36-years period of simulation, two different scenarios for the water table level were performed: one for $H_{ref} = 6.25$ m and one for $H_{ref} = 6.48$ m. For $H_{ref} = 6.25$ m the optimum results

were found after 4 iterations of the simulation – optimization procedure. while for $H_{ref} = 6.48$ m the optimization algorithm was terminated as no feasible solution could be found. Therefore. it is considered that the upper bounds of the feasible solutions maybe should be changed. in order to test if a better solution could be achieved. This will be investigated after getting in contact with the institution that issues the licenses of water use. so as to achieve realistic information.

2. The Fuzzy Optimization Procedure

The optimisation problem that is solved by using the piece-wise linear technique along with the simplex algorithm. it is transformed into a fuzzy problem which will be solved by using the bound and decomposition method for the fully fuzzy linear programming problem within the piece-wise steps. as graphically represented in Figure 34. The current status of the work consists in the completion of writing the algorithm in programming language and fuzzifying some of the variables. For the execution of the entire procedure. the fuzzification of the rest of the variables needs to be completed some amendments need to be done in the algorithm.

Figure 34: Representation of the Fuzzy Optimization Concept

Appendix 1

The Appendix contains the tables for the response matrices, the constraints vectors and the results of the piece-wise linear optimization for the different selected values of the hydraulic head of reference. For the hydraulic heads of reference equal to 6.75 m and 7 m are provided only the results of the pumping rates through the different iterations in order to justify that an optimal solution could not be found.

For $H_{ref} = 6.25$ m

Run 1

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

																			$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$
-42.48	-46.04	-35.28	-14.84	-41.16	-17.30	-45.40	-30.64	-34.76	-67.62	-96.98	-33.11	-44.42	-47.70	-20.49	-25.13	-16.34	-10.00	-55.61	-15.60
-56.49	-49.56	-70.35	-10.75	-61.61	-78.27	-55.74	-7.58	-75.57	-38.96	-22.62	-21.97	-55.34	-53.62	-44.34	-11.70	-4.56	-43.15	-47.50	-17.18
-42.12	-46.47	-34.77	-15.37	-40.55	-17.78	-44.76	-30.54	-34.22	-67.72	-102.95	-33.45	-44.07	-48.11	-19.96	-25.61	-15.87	-9.98	-55.34	-15.48
-56.05	-49.65	-69.57	-10.58	-60.83	-72.47	-55.45	-7.27	-72.78	-38.88	-23.11	-21.96	-55.13	-52.95	-47.09	-11.32	-4.78	-39.14	-47.72	-17.26
-38.61	-53.28	-23.12	-18.75	-30.79	-19.48	-36.50	-26.53	-27.11	-67.19	-105.05	-35.38	-42.43	-40.03	-22.85	-14.39	-16.96	1.49	-58.08	-5.67
-55.36	-52.43	-67.22	-12.07	-59.52	-55.96	-55.43	-8.16	-66.91	-41.05	-24.89	-24.53	-54.87	-53.95	-55.37	-12.71	-5.17	-31.66	-48.88	-19.75
-44.67	-49.24	-38.06	-16.72	-43.74	-18.71	-47.63	-24.79	-37.41	-66.48	-86.68	-38.46	-46.50	-49.93	-22.77	-27.46	-14.82	-10.78	-56.18	-17.70
-54.38	-54.79	-63.40	-13.45	-57.83	-45.55	-54.94	-8.79	-61.64	-43.10	-26.74	-27.35	-54.21	-54.35	-60.19	-13.83	-5.49	-26.35	-49.85	-22.01
-46.84	-52.30	-40.53	-18.45	-45.80	-20.42	-49.25	-21.06	-39.66	-64.54	-64.50	-44.29	-48.09	-51.73	-25.08	-28.10	-13.08	-11.85	-56.29	-19.97
-49.90	-57.91	-47.13	-20.08	-50.19	-25.46	-51.89	-14.40	-45.69	-55.69	-42.10	-48.56	-50.71	-53.97	-33.22	-23.56	-9.31	-14.85	-54.33	-25.76
-52.24	-58.50	-54.43	-17.29	-53.95	-32.53	-53.57	-10.99	-52.40	-48.63	-32.65	-36.52	-52.51	-54.58	-45.58	-18.07	-7.09	-19.04	-52.03	-26.76

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-43.47	-45.79	-35.46	-14.65	-41.29	-17.15	-45.51	-30.51	-34.84	-67.52	-97.01	-33.02	-44.50	-47.64	-20.50	-25.07	-16.36	-9.94	-55.62	-15.55
-56.30	-48.99	-70.30	-10.17	-61.54	-77.44	-55.85	-7.20	-75.48	-38.21	-22.90	-20.99	-55.71	-52.64	-44.65	-10.82	-4.76	-42.37	-47.60	-16.50
-44.04	-45.70	-36.26	-14.45	-42.11	-16.85	-46.28	-29.70	-35.62	-67.00	-103.88	-33.53	-44.98	-47.39	-21.30	-25.14	-16.67	-10.08	-55.65	-15.97
-55.82	-50.12	-69.56	-11.04	-60.84	-72.74	-55.56	-7.81	-72.82	-39.21	-23.26	-22.30	-55.20	-53.38	-47.09	-11.80	-4.75	-39.62	-47.70	-17.74
-51.74	-44.17	-51.92	-13.25	-56.05	-17.35	-58.62	-27.29	-46.63	-70.29	-127.06	-37.71	-50.37	-59.99	-21.21	-38.84	-13.77	-22.77	-56.07	-28.21
-55.44	-52.41	-67.22	-12.05	-59.53	-55.96	-55.43	-8.14	-66.91	-41.04	-24.89	-24.52	-54.86	-53.94	-55.36	-12.67	-5.17	-31.67	-48.86	-19.75
-45.54	-49.36	-38.05	-16.91	-43.66	-18.95	-47.51	-25.06	-37.28	-66.76	-86.19	-39.15	-46.44	-50.03	-22.76	-27.70	-14.70	-11.05	-56.09	-17.90
-54.83	-54.87	-63.67	-13.56	-58.09	-45.68	-55.19	-8.92	-61.86	-43.25	-26.95	-27.51	-54.43	-54.52	-60.10	-14.25	-5.81	-26.45	-49.99	-22.35
-46.86	-52.27	-40.55	-18.42	-45.81	-20.40	-49.26	-21.05	-39.66	-64.52	-64.52	-44.29	-48.07	-51.73	-25.07	-28.10	-13.08	-11.85	-56.29	-19.96
-49.99	-57.88	-47.16	-20.05	-50.22	-25.44	-51.91	-14.37	-45.70	-55.67	-42.11	-48.56	-50.69	-53.97	-33.24	-23.55	-9.30	-14.85	-54.32	-25.75
-52.27	-58.50	-54.44	-17.30	-53.95	-32.54	-53.56	-11.00	-52.40	-48.64	-32.65	-36.52	-52.52	-54.59	-45.60	-18.06	-7.09	-19.04	-52.04	-26.76

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.8124	1	8.6990
2	2.2657	2	8.9334
3	1.8470	3	8.5660
4	2.2502	4	8.8629
5	1.9964	5	8.7893
6	2.2424	6	8.8899
7	1.8862	7	8.5385
8	2.2409	8	8.8511
9	1.9975	9	8.6046
10	2.0776	10	8.6299
11	2.1429	11	8.6917

Optimum Pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.164
2	8,698.63	8,698.63
3	10,257.63	8,687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3,474.58	3,420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.82
8	474.19	381.20
9	1,497.99	815.75
10	1,334.78	1,295.06
11	1,559.42	1,559.42
12	1,099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2,955.60	2,410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.11	140.08
19	1,561.13	267.90
20	162.72	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7486·10 ⁴	3.1254·10 ⁴

Run 2

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-37.70	-45.89	-35.07	-15.79	-41.16	-17.33	-44.63	-30.64	-33.86	-67.57	-97.05	-33.08	-36.22	-47.21	-20.37	-25.27	-16.28	-9.93	-51.12	-16.47
-51.87	-49.26	-70.05	-10.06	-61.58	-78.02	-54.69	-7.30	-74.63	-38.67	-22.73	-21.67	-45.75	-52.67	-44.11	-11.65	-4.37	-43.04	-42.66	-18.25
-32.91	-46.64	-35.47	-12.03	-42.28	-18.52	-51.21	-36.95	-33.60	-70.69	-102.73	-37.53	-34.48	-49.04	-16.29	-33.46	-12.89	-17.47	-50.67	-38.72
-49.90	-49.90	-69.23	-10.90	-60.71	-72.74	-52.64	-7.40	-71.69	-39.02	-23.09	-22.02	-45.47	-52.56	-46.74	-11.24	-4.65	-39.03	-42.87	-16.53
-211.26	-49.86	-33.33	-407.04	-23.68	-105.50	346.99	-183.87	3.99	-116.45	-82.78	-86.12	2.29	-60.20	14.53	-59.83	5.30	-36.02	-50.72	-83.76
-49.88	-52.42	-66.91	-11.75	-59.45	-55.96	-53.72	-8.10	-65.81	-40.98	-24.89	-24.43	-45.33	-53.37	-54.73	-12.55	-5.07	-31.53	-44.03	-19.60
-30.70	-49.26	-37.81	-8.77	-43.56	-18.38	-41.42	-24.29	-35.86	-66.16	-86.38	-37.66	-37.82	-49.15	-22.48	-25.69	-15.05	-8.43	-51.65	-10.75
-48.86	-54.84	-63.21	-13.49	-57.86	-45.64	-52.81	-8.79	-60.55	-43.10	-26.80	-27.33	-44.78	-53.86	-59.56	-13.73	-5.33	-26.11	-45.07	-21.57
-42.47	-52.29	-40.21	-18.32	-45.75	-20.41	-47.66	-21.00	-38.60	-64.48	-64.50	-44.03	-39.43	-51.19	-24.92	-27.97	-13.03	-11.46	-51.67	-19.85
-44.94	-57.90	-46.81	-19.95	-50.14	-25.46	-50.29	-14.34	-44.59	-55.63	-42.11	-48.14	-41.75	-53.43	-33.07	-23.50	-9.25	-14.45	-49.63	-25.63
-47.10	-58.50	-54.11	-17.25	-53.88	-32.53	-51.95	-10.92	-51.26	-48.57	-32.65	-36.40	-43.32	-54.02	-45.17	-17.98	-7.01	-18.62	-47.27	-26.49

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-58.83	-45.93	-36.05	-12.72	-41.34	-17.16	-47.86	-30.69	-38.12	-67.64	-96.96	-33.14	-98.56	-48.79	-20.91	-24.88	-16.54	-11.42	-104.52	-13.98
-72.84	-49.28	-71.04	-12.72	-61.64	-77.67	-58.91	-7.61	-79.07	-38.53	-22.76	-21.36	-120.36	-54.31	-45.26	-10.77	-5.36	-44.26	-99.29	-15.06
-70.04	-45.55	-35.87	-23.85	-40.44	-16.08	-39.76	-21.51	-38.98	-63.94	-104.08	-28.93	-105.67	-46.72	-26.07	-13.64	-21.91	18.56	-106.01	23.67
-75.18	-49.87	-70.35	-11.13	-61.02	-72.46	-61.11	-7.87	-76.74	-39.15	-23.28	-22.30	-119.41	-54.52	-47.55	-12.20	-4.92	-43.55	-99.29	-19.36
238.60	-47.36	-43.00	1096.91	-63.68	68.55	-556.66	167.63	-113.51	-19.84	-149.29	20.20	-250.19	-38.17	-66.45	21.53	-48.28	88.52	-117.21	97.89
-73.31	-52.42	-67.99	-12.72	-59.65	-55.94	-58.91	-8.13	-70.73	-41.16	-24.88	-24.72	-118.46	-55.23	-56.43	-12.92	-5.36	-33.55	-100.41	-19.36
-78.44	-49.35	-38.69	-39.74	-43.89	-19.23	-56.70	-25.71	-41.68	-67.10	-86.44	-40.19	-102.82	-51.53	-23.20	-30.62	-14.31	-22.13	-104.89	-30.12
-72.84	-54.82	-64.31	-14.31	-58.13	-45.62	-59.64	-8.92	-65.71	-43.32	-26.87	-27.67	-117.51	-55.76	-61.30	-14.59	-6.26	-28.55	-101.53	-23.67
-62.10	-52.28	-41.25	-19.08	-45.94	-20.42	-53.01	-21.25	-43.40	-64.63	-64.51	-44.71	-105.19	-52.94	-25.49	-28.71	-13.41	-14.99	-106.01	-20.44
-66.30	-57.88	-47.87	-20.67	-50.32	-25.42	-55.22	-14.43	-49.40	-55.75	-42.07	-49.23	-109.93	-55.18	-33.51	-23.92	-9.39	-17.85	-104.52	-25.82
-69.57	-58.50	-55.17	-19.08	-54.09	-32.59	-57.43	-11.28	-56.27	-48.80	-32.64	-36.82	-114.20	-55.89	-46.40	-18.42	-7.60	-22.13	-103.02	-27.97

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.812	1	8.6990
2	2.266	2	8.9334
3	1.847	3	8.5660
4	2.250	4	8.8629
5	1.996	5	8.7893
6	2.242	6	8.8899
7	1.886	7	8.5385
8	2.241	8	8.8511
9	1.998	9	8.6046
10	2.078	10	8.6299
11	2.143	11	8.6917

Optimum Pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.164
2	8,698.63	8,698.63
3	10,257.63	8,687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3,474.58	3,420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.82
8	474.19	381.20
9	1,497.99	815.75
10	1,334.78	1,295.06
11	1,559.42	1,559.42
12	1,099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2,955.60	2,410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.11	140.08
19	1,561.13	267.90
20	162.72	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7486·10 ⁴	3.1254·10 ⁴

For $H_{ref} = 6.5$ m

Run 1

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-42.48	-46.04	-35.28	-14.84	-41.16	-17.30	-45.40	-30.64	-34.76	-67.62	-96.98	-33.11	-44.42	-47.70	-20.49	-25.13	-16.34	-10.00	-55.61	-15.60
-56.49	-49.56	-70.35	-10.75	-61.61	-78.27	-55.74	-7.58	-75.57	-38.96	-22.62	-21.97	-55.34	-53.62	-44.34	-11.70	-4.56	-43.15	-47.50	-17.18
-42.12	-46.47	-34.77	-15.37	-40.55	-17.78	-44.76	-30.54	-34.22	-67.72	-102.95	-33.45	-44.07	-48.11	-19.96	-25.61	-15.87	-9.98	-55.34	-15.48
-56.05	-49.65	-69.57	-10.58	-60.83	-72.47	-55.45	-7.27	-72.78	-38.88	-23.11	-21.96	-55.13	-52.95	-47.09	-11.32	-4.78	-39.14	-47.72	-17.26
-38.61	-53.28	-23.12	-18.75	-30.79	-19.48	-36.50	-26.53	-27.11	-67.19	-105.05	-35.38	-42.43	-40.03	-22.85	-14.39	-16.96	1.49	-58.08	-5.67
-55.36	-52.43	-67.22	-12.07	-59.52	-55.96	-55.43	-8.16	-66.91	-41.05	-24.89	-24.53	-54.87	-53.95	-55.37	-12.71	-5.17	-31.66	-48.88	-19.75
-44.67	-49.24	-38.06	-16.72	-43.74	-18.71	-47.63	-24.79	-37.41	-66.48	-86.68	-38.46	-46.50	-49.93	-22.77	-27.46	-14.82	-10.78	-56.18	-17.70
-54.38	-54.79	-63.40	-13.45	-57.83	-45.55	-54.94	-8.79	-61.64	-43.10	-26.74	-27.35	-54.21	-54.35	-60.19	-13.83	-5.49	-26.35	-49.85	-22.01
-46.84	-52.30	-40.53	-18.45	-45.80	-20.42	-49.25	-21.06	-39.66	-64.54	-64.50	-44.29	-48.09	-51.73	-25.08	-28.10	-13.08	-11.85	-56.29	-19.97
-49.90	-57.91	-47.13	-20.08	-50.19	-25.46	-51.89	-14.40	-45.69	-55.69	-42.10	-48.56	-50.71	-53.97	-33.22	-23.56	-9.31	-14.85	-54.33	-25.76
-52.24	-58.50	-54.43	-17.29	-53.95	-32.53	-53.57	-10.99	-52.40	-48.63	-32.65	-36.52	-52.51	-54.58	-45.58	-18.07	-7.09	-19.04	-52.03	-26.76

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-43.47	-45.79	-35.46	-14.65	-41.29	-17.15	-45.51	-30.51	-34.84	-67.52	-97.01	-33.02	-44.50	-47.64	-20.50	-25.07	-16.36	-9.94	-55.62	-15.55
-56.30	-48.99	-70.30	-10.17	-61.54	-77.44	-55.85	-7.20	-75.48	-38.21	-22.90	-20.99	-55.71	-52.64	-44.65	-10.82	-4.76	-42.37	-47.60	-16.50
-44.04	-45.70	-36.26	-14.45	-42.11	-16.85	-46.28	-29.70	-35.62	-67.00	-103.88	-33.53	-44.98	-47.39	-21.30	-25.14	-16.67	-10.08	-55.65	-15.97
-55.82	-50.12	-69.56	-11.04	-60.84	-72.74	-55.56	-7.81	-72.82	-39.21	-23.26	-22.30	-55.20	-53.38	-47.09	-11.80	-4.75	-39.62	-47.70	-17.74
-51.74	-44.17	-51.92	-13.25	-56.05	-17.35	-58.62	-27.29	-46.63	-70.29	-127.06	-37.71	-50.37	-59.99	-21.21	-38.84	-13.77	-22.77	-56.07	-28.21
-55.44	-52.41	-67.22	-12.05	-59.53	-55.96	-55.43	-8.14	-66.91	-41.04	-24.89	-24.52	-54.86	-53.94	-55.36	-12.67	-5.17	-31.67	-48.86	-19.75
-45.54	-49.36	-38.05	-16.91	-43.66	-18.95	-47.51	-25.06	-37.28	-66.76	-86.19	-39.15	-46.44	-50.03	-22.76	-27.70	-14.70	-11.05	-56.09	-17.90
-54.83	-54.87	-63.67	-13.56	-58.09	-45.68	-55.19	-8.92	-61.86	-43.25	-26.95	-27.51	-54.43	-54.52	-60.10	-14.25	-5.81	-26.45	-49.99	-22.35
-46.86	-52.27	-40.55	-18.42	-45.81	-20.40	-49.26	-21.05	-39.66	-64.52	-64.52	-44.29	-48.07	-51.73	-25.07	-28.10	-13.08	-11.85	-56.29	-19.96
-49.99	-57.88	-47.16	-20.05	-50.22	-25.44	-51.91	-14.37	-45.70	-55.67	-42.11	-48.56	-50.69	-53.97	-33.24	-23.55	-9.30	-14.85	-54.32	-25.75
-52.27	-58.50	-54.44	-17.30	-53.95	-32.54	-53.56	-11.00	-52.40	-48.64	-32.65	-36.52	-52.52	-54.59	-45.60	-18.06	-7.09	-19.04	-52.04	-26.76

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.5624	1	8.4490
2	2.0157	2	8.6834
3	1.5970	3	8.3160
4	2.0002	4	8.6129
5	1.7464	5	8.5393
6	1.9924	6	8.6399
7	1.6362	7	8.2885
8	1.9909	8	8.6011
9	1.7475	9	8.3546
10	1.8276	10	8.3799
11	1.8929	11	8.4417

Optimum pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.16
2	8,698.63	8,698.63
3	10,257.63	8,687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3,474.58	3,420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.81
8	474.19	381.20
9	1,371.23	815.75
10	1,334.78	1,295.06
11	1,280.68	1,559.42
12	1,099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2,955.60	2,410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	1,561.13	267.90
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7080·10 ⁴	3.1254·10 ⁴

Run 2

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-37.80	-45.90	-35.06	-14.89	-41.16	-17.22	-44.40	-30.49	-33.95	-67.49	-87.57	-32.95	-36.36	-47.17	-20.27	-25.07	-16.34	-9.64	-51.14	-15.61
-45.57	-49.40	-70.00	-19.33	-61.19	-80.44	-45.88	-11.92	-73.77	-40.11	-21.06	-23.14	-44.78	-53.12	-42.94	-13.43	-3.56	-44.66	-42.57	-22.98
-44.02	-46.30	-35.64	-9.61	-42.67	-17.29	-64.42	-32.71	-35.84	-68.87	-100.22	-37.02	-37.64	-47.99	-25.24	-29.43	-19.48	-15.90	-51.26	-40.56
-49.11	-49.69	-69.30	-4.55	-60.75	-71.67	-53.95	-5.02	-72.05	-38.10	-20.46	-20.92	-45.91	-52.18	-47.39	-9.54	-5.16	-37.32	-42.92	-11.25
-279.30	-49.32	-40.43	-251.82	-47.02	-75.43	-91.54	-139.92	-42.52	-107.10	-134.85	-75.26	-36.84	-74.03	12.54	-150.58	21.44	-138.58	-48.00	-417.21
-49.80	-52.42	-66.91	-11.75	-59.47	-55.90	-54.12	-7.99	-65.97	-40.97	-22.31	-24.42	-45.35	-53.37	-54.75	-12.57	-5.07	-31.56	-44.03	-19.73
-35.66	-49.31	-37.76	-14.44	-43.54	-19.01	-42.28	-25.45	-35.98	-66.66	-81.74	-39.47	-37.79	-49.27	-22.64	-27.08	-14.18	-10.18	-51.49	-15.61
-49.14	-54.73	-63.31	-9.55	-57.98	-45.32	-53.84	-8.50	-60.74	-43.04	-24.31	-27.28	-44.83	-53.85	-59.61	-13.70	-5.35	-26.07	-45.07	-21.51
-42.59	-52.30	-40.22	-18.38	-45.75	-20.43	-47.66	-21.05	-38.72	-64.50	-59.25	-44.01	-39.42	-51.20	-24.94	-28.00	-13.06	-11.50	-51.67	-19.97
-44.68	-57.88	-46.80	-19.84	-50.13	-25.37	-50.23	-14.15	-44.70	-55.57	-40.10	-48.05	-41.73	-53.40	-33.07	-23.36	-9.25	-14.28	-49.63	-25.01
-46.95	-58.50	-54.11	-17.25	-53.88	-32.55	-51.83	-10.94	-51.38	-48.58	-30.17	-36.40	-43.32	-54.02	-45.17	-17.98	-7.04	-18.62	-47.27	-26.49

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-58.83	-45.92	-36.05	-14.31	-41.32	-17.16	-47.86	-30.69	-37.51	-67.64	-86.19	-33.24	-98.09	-48.79	-20.91	-25.12	-16.09	-12.14	-104.14	-15.06
-84.05	-49.15	-71.10	14.31	-62.05	-75.28	-70.69	-1.84	-80.17	-37.14	-19.49	-19.67	-124.15	-53.77	-46.69	-8.37	-6.71	-38.55	-100.04	-6.45
-49.49	-45.88	-35.68	-30.20	-40.06	-17.38	-23.56	-27.02	-34.81	-65.87	-97.98	-29.46	-93.35	-48.01	-15.18	-19.62	-11.62	12.14	-103.02	26.89
-76.11	-50.09	-70.27	-28.61	-60.99	-73.54	-59.64	-10.76	-75.64	-40.08	-19.11	-23.67	-117.99	-55.02	-46.98	-14.83	-4.47	-50.68	-98.92	-29.05
369.81	-48.01	-34.58	654.97	-39.97	38.56	6.63	113.33	-28.81	-29.34	-142.62	9.26	-109.93	-20.99	-65.02	155.99	-74.22	498.99	-132.88	680.95
-73.31	-52.42	-67.99	-12.72	-59.65	-55.94	-58.91	-8.39	-69.87	-41.16	-20.91	-24.72	-118.46	-55.23	-56.43	-12.92	-5.36	-33.55	-100.41	-19.36
-69.57	-49.31	-38.75	-25.44	-43.95	-18.68	-56.70	-24.40	-41.07	-66.72	-79.52	-38.29	-103.30	-51.41	-23.20	-28.71	-16.09	-15.71	-106.01	-22.59
-72.37	-54.95	-64.21	-25.44	-58.01	-45.95	-58.91	-9.44	-64.97	-43.40	-22.96	-27.77	-117.99	-55.81	-61.30	-14.83	-6.26	-29.27	-101.53	-24.74
-62.10	-52.28	-41.25	-19.08	-45.94	-20.42	-53.01	-21.25	-42.66	-64.63	-58.10	-44.71	-105.19	-52.94	-25.49	-28.47	-13.41	-14.99	-106.01	-20.44
-66.77	-57.91	-47.88	-22.26	-50.35	-25.53	-55.96	-14.69	-48.79	-55.83	-38.60	-49.34	-110.41	-55.27	-33.80	-24.16	-9.39	-18.56	-104.89	-27.97
-70.04	-58.50	-55.17	-19.08	-54.09	-32.59	-57.43	-11.28	-55.53	-48.80	-28.92	-36.82	-113.72	-55.85	-46.40	-18.42	-7.60	-22.13	-103.02	-27.97

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.5492	1	8.4327
2	2.0219	2	8.6708
3	1.6354	3	8.2665
4	1.9858	4	8.6180
5	2.4301	5	7.9211
6	1.9888	6	8.6334
7	1.6254	7	8.2840
8	1.9860	8	8.5976
9	1.7405	9	8.3451
10	1.8237	10	8.3762
11	1.8894	11	8.4370

Optimum pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.16
2	8,698.63	8,698.63
3	10,257.63	8,687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3,474.58	3,420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.81
8	474.19	381.20
9	1,498.00	815.75
10	1,334.78	1,295.06
11	1,472.43	1,559.42
12	1,099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2,955.60	2,410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	1,561.13	267.90
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7399·10 ⁴	3.1254·10 ⁴

Run 3

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-38.34	-45.90	-35.06	-14.39	-41.17	-17.18	-44.14	-30.49	-33.80	-67.49	-97.27	-32.94	-36.22	-47.15	-20.38	-24.96	-16.31	-9.59	-51.13	-15.33
-51.80	-49.27	-70.04	-10.17	-61.57	-78.04	-54.61	-7.33	-74.63	-38.68	-22.80	-21.68	-45.74	-52.67	-44.11	-11.65	-4.37	-43.04	-42.66	-18.25
-39.14	-45.94	-35.27	-5.28	-41.46	-15.78	-45.83	-27.84	-33.93	-66.67	-103.52	-32.37	-36.13	-47.11	-19.03	-24.63	-15.19	-8.46	-50.93	-10.23
-49.83	-49.90	-69.23	-11.04	-60.70	-72.76	-52.52	-7.42	-71.68	-39.02	-23.14	-22.02	-45.45	-52.56	-46.74	-11.24	-4.64	-39.02	-42.86	-16.53
-66.54	-46.64	-36.96	39.79	-41.17	-10.91	8.12	-14.41	-29.20	-64.37	-106.25	-32.77	-32.46	-44.18	-26.25	3.09	-22.63	21.64	-53.48	84.77
-50.03	-52.42	-66.91	-11.75	-59.46	-55.95	-53.75	-8.09	-65.81	-40.98	-24.96	-24.42	-45.33	-53.36	-54.73	-12.55	-5.09	-31.53	-44.02	-19.60
-39.22	-49.33	-37.74	-17.56	-43.60	-19.10	-44.97	-25.42	-36.20	-66.72	-86.68	-38.60	-37.89	-49.53	-22.38	-27.65	-14.81	-10.59	-51.61	-17.94
-49.09	-54.83	-63.22	-13.18	-57.87	-45.59	-53.01	-8.72	-60.57	-43.09	-26.88	-27.31	-44.80	-53.85	-59.59	-13.73	-5.34	-26.10	-45.07	-21.57
-42.05	-52.29	-40.21	-18.38	-45.75	-20.41	-47.72	-21.01	-38.60	-64.48	-64.65	-44.04	-39.44	-51.20	-24.93	-27.98	-13.06	-11.46	-51.68	-19.85
-44.86	-57.90	-46.80	-20.03	-50.14	-25.47	-50.23	-14.36	-44.59	-55.63	-42.15	-48.14	-41.75	-53.43	-33.08	-23.51	-9.24	-14.45	-49.63	-25.60
-47.08	-58.50	-54.11	-17.22	-53.88	-32.53	-51.92	-10.92	-51.26	-48.57	-32.71	-36.39	-43.31	-54.02	-45.16	-17.98	-7.02	-18.63	-47.27	-26.49

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-6}$																			
-58.13	-45.92	-36.06	-15.90	-41.33	-17.22	-48.60	-30.69	-38.25	-67.68	-96.61	-33.24	-98.56	-48.84	-20.77	-25.36	-16.32	-12.49	-104.33	-16.14
-73.07	-49.28	-71.05	-11.92	-61.65	-77.67	-59.27	-7.61	-79.19	-38.57	-22.67	-21.36	-120.59	-54.31	-45.26	-10.89	-5.36	-44.62	-99.48	-14.52
-57.20	-46.23	-36.12	-42.92	-41.27	-18.85	-46.76	-33.05	-38.43	-68.11	-103.24	-34.87	-99.51	-49.08	-22.77	-26.68	-18.11	-17.85	-104.70	-25.82
-75.41	-49.87	-70.35	-10.33	-61.02	-72.46	-61.11	-7.74	-76.80	-39.15	-23.18	-22.36	-119.64	-54.52	-47.69	-12.20	-5.14	-43.55	-99.29	-19.36
-14.01	-50.78	-38.60	-172.48	-45.83	-25.85	-120.76	-42.37	-52.65	-73.28	-125.69	-41.08	-121.78	-57.69	-16.90	-70.70	-3.80	-140.99	-101.16	-194.71
-73.54	-52.42	-68.01	-13.51	-59.66	-56.00	-59.64	-8.39	-70.79	-41.20	-24.78	-24.78	-118.70	-55.27	-56.57	-13.16	-5.59	-34.27	-100.41	-20.44
-63.04	-49.28	-38.77	-15.90	-43.87	-18.58	-52.65	-24.40	-41.13	-66.60	-86.12	-39.19	-102.82	-51.08	-23.49	-27.87	-14.98	-13.92	-105.26	-18.29
-72.84	-54.84	-64.30	-15.10	-58.11	-45.62	-59.64	-9.18	-65.71	-43.32	-26.77	-27.72	-117.75	-55.76	-61.30	-14.71	-6.26	-29.27	-101.53	-23.67
-62.80	-52.28	-41.26	-19.08	-45.94	-20.37	-52.65	-21.12	-43.33	-64.63	-64.32	-44.71	-105.19	-52.94	-25.35	-28.59	-13.19	-14.63	-106.01	-20.44
-66.77	-57.89	-47.87	-20.67	-50.34	-25.42	-55.59	-14.43	-49.46	-55.75	-42.00	-49.23	-110.17	-55.20	-33.51	-23.92	-9.39	-17.49	-104.70	-26.36
-69.57	-58.50	-55.17	-18.28	-54.08	-32.53	-57.43	-11.15	-56.27	-48.76	-32.54	-36.82	-113.96	-55.87	-46.40	-18.42	-7.38	-21.77	-102.84	-27.97

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	1.5622	1	8.4486
2	2.0183	2	8.6811
3	1.5883	3	8.3251
4	1.9988	4	8.6142
5	1.6023	5	8.6829
6	1.9924	6	8.6403
7	1.6365	7	8.2885
8	1.9901	8	8.6021
9	1.7475	9	8.3541
10	1.8277	10	8.3795
11	1.8929	11	8.4418

Optimum pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	392.55	214.16
2	8698.63	8698.63
3	10257.63	8687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	3474.58	3420.03
6	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	135.81
8	474.19	381.20
9	1498.00	815.75
10	1334.78	1295.06
11	1464.07	1559.42
12	1099.19	950.55
13	782.12	211.04
14	2955.60	2410.14
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	1561.13	267.90
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	3.7390·10 ⁴	3.1254·10 ⁴

For $H_{ref} = 6.75$ m Optimum Results for the Dry Season

Pumping Well	Qopt1	Qopt2	Qopt3	Qopt4	Qopt5	Qopt6	Qopt7	Qopt8	Qopt9b	Qopt9a	Qopt11
1	392.55	237.96	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55
2	8,698.63	8,698.63	8,698.63	8,698.63	8,698.63	8,698.63	8,698.63	8,698.63	8,698.63	8,698.63	8,698.63
3	9,683.17	10,257.63	10,257.63	7,784.96	8,161.91	10,257.63	10,257.63	10,257.63	7,804.13	7803.26	10,257.63
4	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94
5	3,474.58	3474.58	3,474.58	3,474.58	3,474.58	2,435.08	168.90	3474.58	3,474.58	3,474.58	1,226.12
6	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	174.79	45.54	174.79	174.79	0.00	174.79	174.79	174.79	174.79	174.79
8	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19
9	0.00	1,498.00	1,498.00	1,498.00	1,498.00	276.49	1,498.00	1,498.00	1,498.00	1,498.00	816.13
10	0.00	1,334.78	1,334.78	279.19	1,334.78	0.00	1,334.78	1,334.78	165.98	178.27	1,334.78
11	874.37	1,559.42	1,559.42	532.47	94.24	1,301.42	387.17	1,559.42	581.69	565.06	193.18
12	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19
13	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12
14	2,955.60	2,955.60	2,955.60	2,955.60	1,890.88	2,955.60	2,955.60	2,955.60	2,955.60	2,955.60	2,955.60
15	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64
16	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43
17	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78
18	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10
19	618.71	1,561.13	1,561.13	1,561.13	1,561.13	1,561.13	1,561.13	1,561.13	1,561.13	1,561.13	1,561.13
20	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73
Total pumping rate	$3.2451 \cdot 10^4$	$3.7331 \cdot 10^4$	$3.7357 \cdot 10^4$	$3.2931 \cdot 10^4$	$3.2860 \cdot 10^4$	$3.3457 \cdot 10^4$	$3.3008 \cdot 10^4$	$3.7486 \cdot 10^4$	$3.2886 \cdot 10^4$	$3.2881 \cdot 10^4$	$3.3189 \cdot 10^4$

For $H_{ref} = 7$ m Optimum Results for the Dry Season

Pumping Well	Qopt1	Qopt2	Qopt3	Qopt4	Qopt5	Qopt6a	Qopt6b
1	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	392.55	0.00
2	8,654.54	7,134.81	8,698.63	8,698.63	7,671.64	8,698.63	8,698.63
3	8,990.56	10,257.63	8,901.43	8,091.44	6,360.73	10,257.63	10,257.63
4	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94	177.94
5	3,474.58	0.00	3474.58	1,828.31	3,474.58	0.00	2,422.00
6	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55	920.55
7	174.79	0.00	174.79	174.79	174.79	174.79	0.00
8	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19	474.19
9	0.00	422.38	1,498.00	1,498.00	1,498.00	512.46	1,498.00
10	0.00	0.00	1,334.78	0.00	0.00	358.29	989.81
11	377.82	0.00	942.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
12	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19	1,099.19
13	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12	782.12
14	0.00	2,955.60	2,955.60	0.00	2,955.60	890.43	2,955.60
15	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64	426.64
16	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43	617.43
17	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78	356.78
18	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10	561.10
19	0.00	1,561.13	1,561.13	1,561.13	122.13	1,561.13	1,561.13
20	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73	162.73
Total pumping rate	$2.7644 \cdot 10^4$	$2.8303 \cdot 10^4$	$3.5512 \cdot 10^4$	$2.7824 \cdot 10^4$	$2.8229 \cdot 10^4$	$2.8425 \cdot 10^4$	$3.3961 \cdot 10^4$

Appendix 2

For $H_{ref} = 6.25$ m

Run 1

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.27	-4.60	-3.53	-1.48	-4.12	-1.72	-4.55	-3.06	-3.48	-6.76	-9.70	-3.31	-4.45	-4.77	-2.05	-2.51	-1.63	-1.00	-5.56	-1.56
-5.63	-4.93	-7.03	-1.05	-6.16	-7.78	-5.60	-0.71	-7.57	-3.84	-2.28	-2.14	-5.55	-5.31	-4.45	-1.13	-0.47	-4.28	-4.76	-1.68
-4.29	-4.62	-3.55	-1.50	-4.14	-1.74	-4.56	-3.02	-3.50	-6.74	-10.36	-3.35	-4.43	-4.82	-2.03	-2.57	-1.61	-1.02	-5.54	-1.58
-5.59	-4.99	-6.96	-1.08	-6.08	-7.26	-5.55	-0.76	-7.27	-3.91	-2.31	-2.22	-5.51	-5.32	-4.71	-1.16	-0.48	-3.94	-4.77	-1.75
-4.50	-4.89	-3.77	-1.61	-4.36	-1.86	-4.77	-2.70	-3.70	-6.89	-11.27	-4.42	-3.96	-5.51	-1.91	-2.87	-1.44	-1.15	-5.68	-1.73
-5.53	-5.25	-6.72	-1.21	-5.95	-5.60	-5.54	-0.82	-6.69	-4.10	-2.49	-2.45	-5.49	-5.39	-5.54	-1.27	-0.52	-3.17	-4.89	-1.98
-4.49	-4.93	-3.80	-1.68	-4.37	-1.88	-4.76	-2.49	-3.73	-6.66	-8.65	-3.88	-4.64	-4.99	-2.28	-2.75	-1.48	-1.09	-5.62	-1.78
-5.45	-5.49	-6.35	-1.35	-5.80	-4.56	-5.51	-0.89	-6.18	-4.32	-2.69	-2.74	-5.43	-5.45	-6.02	-1.41	-0.56	-2.65	-4.99	-2.22
-4.67	-5.23	-4.05	-1.84	-4.58	-2.04	-4.93	-2.11	-3.97	-6.45	-6.45	-4.43	-4.81	-5.17	-2.51	-2.81	-1.31	-1.18	-5.63	-2.00
-4.98	-5.79	-4.71	-2.01	-5.02	-2.55	-5.19	-1.44	-4.57	-5.57	-4.21	-4.86	-5.07	-5.40	-3.32	-2.36	-0.93	-1.49	-5.43	-2.58
-5.21	-5.85	-5.44	-1.73	-5.39	-3.25	-5.36	-1.10	-5.24	-4.86	-3.26	-3.65	-5.25	-5.46	-4.56	-1.81	-0.71	-1.90	-5.20	-2.68

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.27	-4.60	-3.53	-1.48	-4.12	-1.72	-4.55	-3.06	-3.48	-6.76	-9.70	-3.31	-4.45	-4.77	-2.05	-2.51	-1.63	-1.00	-5.56	-1.56
-5.63	-4.93	-7.03	-1.05	-6.16	-7.78	-5.60	-0.71	-7.57	-3.85	-2.28	-2.14	-5.56	-5.31	-4.45	-1.13	-0.47	-4.28	-4.76	-1.68
-4.29	-4.62	-3.55	-1.50	-4.14	-1.74	-4.56	-3.02	-3.50	-6.74	-10.36	-3.35	-4.43	-4.82	-2.03	-2.57	-1.61	-1.02	-5.54	-1.58
-5.59	-4.99	-6.96	-1.08	-6.08	-7.26	-5.55	-0.76	-7.27	-3.91	-2.31	-2.22	-5.51	-5.32	-4.71	-1.16	-0.48	-3.94	-4.77	-1.75
-4.50	-4.89	-3.77	-1.61	-4.36	-1.86	-4.77	-2.70	-3.70	-6.89	-11.27	-4.42	-3.96	-5.50	-1.91	-2.87	-1.44	-1.15	-5.68	-1.73
-5.53	-5.25	-6.72	-1.21	-5.95	-5.60	-5.54	-0.82	-6.69	-4.10	-2.49	-2.45	-5.49	-5.39	-5.54	-1.27	-0.52	-3.17	-4.89	-1.98
-4.49	-4.93	-3.80	-1.68	-4.37	-1.88	-4.76	-2.49	-3.73	-6.66	-8.65	-3.88	-4.64	-4.99	-2.28	-2.75	-1.48	-1.09	-5.61	-1.78
-5.45	-5.49	-6.35	-1.35	-5.80	-4.56	-5.51	-0.89	-6.18	-4.32	-2.69	-2.74	-5.43	-5.45	-6.02	-1.41	-0.56	-2.65	-4.99	-2.22
-4.67	-5.23	-4.05	-1.84	-4.58	-2.04	-4.93	-2.11	-3.97	-6.45	-6.45	-4.43	-4.81	-5.17	-2.51	-2.81	-1.31	-1.18	-5.63	-2.00
-4.98	-5.79	-4.71	-2.01	-5.02	-2.55	-5.19	-1.44	-4.57	-5.57	-4.21	-4.86	-5.07	-5.40	-3.32	-2.36	-0.93	-1.49	-5.43	-2.58
-5.21	-5.85	-5.44	-1.73	-5.39	-3.25	-5.36	-1.10	-5.24	-4.86	-3.26	-3.65	-5.25	-5.46	-4.56	-1.81	-0.71	-1.90	-5.20	-2.68

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	0.25575	1	0.625884
2	0.560789	2	0.964381
3	0.231448	3	0.600089
4	0.539786	4	0.941123
5	0.402736	5	0.779808
6	0.571875	6	0.971935
7	0.316662	7	0.689067
8	0.577519	8	0.97503
9	0.411407	9	0.788718
10	0.491845	10	0.875317
11	0.527572	11	0.916835

Optimum Pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	4,667.93
3	1,989.94	8,441.07
4	177.94	62.90
5	0.00	0.00
6	920.55	920.55
7	0.00	0.00
8	474.19	381.20
9	1,498.00	0.00
10	0.00	0.00
11	0.00	0.00
12	1,099.19	950.55
13	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.00
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	0.00	0.00
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	8284.49	16648.01

Run 2

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.30	-4.64	-1.82	-1.42	-4.12	-1.72	-4.55	-3.05	-2.16	-6.76	-9.70	-3.29	-4.45	-4.77	-2.02	-2.48	-1.63	-0.92	-5.56	-1.49
-5.64	-5.00	-5.16	-0.78	-6.15	-7.76	-5.57	-0.66	-6.18	-3.86	-2.27	-2.12	-5.55	-5.31	-4.42	-1.10	-0.45	-4.17	-4.76	-1.63
-4.31	-4.66	-1.85	-1.36	-4.14	-1.71	-4.56	-2.97	-2.16	-6.74	-10.36	-3.33	-4.43	-4.82	-2.32	-2.31	-1.80	-0.80	-5.54	-1.26
-5.60	-5.05	-5.06	-1.15	-6.09	-7.27	-5.55	-0.76	-5.89	-3.90	-2.32	-2.20	-5.52	-5.32	-4.66	-1.13	-0.46	-3.86	-4.77	-1.71
-4.53	-4.94	-2.02	-1.29	-4.36	-1.78	-4.77	-2.57	-2.29	-6.89	-11.28	-0.80	-3.96	-5.51	-5.01	-1.30	-2.67	-0.42	-5.68	-0.75
-5.54	-5.30	-4.75	-1.15	-5.95	-5.59	-5.54	-0.80	-5.28	-4.11	-2.49	-2.43	-5.49	-5.39	-5.45	-1.24	-0.50	-3.12	-4.89	-1.93
-4.51	-4.98	-2.04	-1.67	-4.37	-1.89	-4.76	-2.49	-2.39	-6.66	-8.65	-3.88	-4.65	-4.99	-2.20	-2.78	-1.42	-1.07	-5.62	-1.83
-5.46	-5.54	-4.45	-1.29	-5.80	-4.56	-5.51	-0.87	-4.73	-4.32	-2.69	-2.73	-5.43	-5.44	-5.95	-1.38	-0.54	-2.59	-4.99	-2.18
-4.69	-5.28	-2.26	-1.80	-4.58	-2.04	-4.93	-2.09	-2.58	-6.45	-6.45	-4.39	-4.81	-5.17	-2.48	-2.77	-1.29	-1.12	-5.63	-1.96
-4.99	-5.85	-2.90	-1.94	-5.02	-2.54	-5.19	-1.43	-3.13	-5.57	-4.21	-4.80	-5.07	-5.40	-3.29	-2.33	-0.91	-1.42	-5.43	-2.51
-5.23	-5.91	-3.65	-1.68	-5.40	-3.25	-5.36	-1.08	-3.78	-4.86	-3.27	-3.62	-5.25	-5.46	-4.49	-1.78	-0.69	-1.84	-5.20	-2.59

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.30	-4.53	-3.02	-1.55	-4.12	-1.72	-4.55	-3.07	-2.85	-6.76	-9.70	-3.33	-4.45	-4.77	-2.09	-2.54	-1.67	-1.26	-5.56	-1.57
-5.64	-4.88	-6.43	-0.56	-6.15	-7.77	-5.57	-0.67	-6.79	-3.86	-2.27	-2.17	-5.55	-5.31	-4.49	-1.17	-0.49	-4.49	-4.76	-1.75
-4.31	-4.55	-3.04	-1.37	-4.14	-1.71	-4.56	-2.98	-2.87	-6.74	-10.36	-3.37	-4.43	-4.82	-2.44	-2.27	-1.94	-0.75	-5.54	-1.15
-5.60	-4.92	-6.35	-1.54	-6.09	-7.27	-5.55	-0.79	-6.53	-3.90	-2.32	-2.24	-5.52	-5.32	-4.73	-1.20	-0.49	-4.23	-4.77	-1.81
-4.53	-4.82	-3.22	-0.95	-4.36	-1.78	-4.77	-2.57	-3.06	-6.89	-11.27	-0.39	-3.96	-5.50	-5.68	-0.74	-3.37	0.95	-5.68	-0.18
-5.54	-5.18	-6.14	-1.30	-5.95	-5.59	-5.54	-0.83	-5.94	-4.11	-2.49	-2.48	-5.49	-5.39	-5.50	-1.31	-0.53	-3.55	-4.89	-2.03
-4.51	-4.87	-3.28	-1.86	-4.37	-1.89	-4.76	-2.52	-3.09	-6.66	-8.65	-3.92	-4.65	-4.99	-2.25	-2.87	-1.42	-1.55	-5.62	-1.99
-5.46	-5.42	-5.77	-1.42	-5.80	-4.56	-5.51	-0.90	-5.44	-4.32	-2.69	-2.77	-5.43	-5.44	-5.98	-1.45	-0.57	-3.04	-4.99	-2.28
-4.69	-5.17	-3.52	-1.94	-4.58	-2.04	-4.93	-2.12	-3.31	-6.45	-6.45	-4.43	-4.81	-5.17	-2.55	-2.83	-1.33	-1.48	-5.63	-2.05
-4.99	-5.73	-4.15	-2.07	-5.02	-2.54	-5.19	-1.45	-3.89	-5.57	-4.21	-4.83	-5.07	-5.40	-3.36	-2.39	-0.95	-1.81	-5.43	-2.60
-5.23	-5.79	-4.86	-1.83	-5.40	-3.25	-5.36	-1.11	-4.54	-4.86	-3.27	-3.67	-5.25	-5.46	-4.56	-1.85	-0.73	-2.26	-5.20	-2.68

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	0.170887	1	0.618106
2	0.468399	2	0.954911
3	0.145829	3	0.591311
4	0.447511	4	0.931995
5	0.286443	5	0.742434
6	0.476985	6	0.96311
7	0.231277	7	0.682364
8	0.484894	8	0.96629
9	0.323963	9	0.781167
10	0.401887	10	0.866677
11	0.437315	11	0.907538

Optimum Pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	0	0
2	0	5,452.431251
3	6,206.541946	8,514.706861
4	177.9414928	62.90410959
5	0	0
6	920.5479452	920.5479452
7	0	0
8	0	381.2
9	0	0
10	0	0
11	0	0
12	0	950.5479452
13	0	0
14	0	0
15	0	349.1123288
16	0	417.9863014
17	356.7814492	223.6739726
18	561.1008834	140.0821918
19	0	0
20	162.7252592	92.95890411
Total pumping rate	8,385.638976	17,506.15181

Run 3

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.30	-4.92	-2.76	-1.44	-4.12	-1.72	-4.55	-3.04	-3.48	-6.76	-9.70	-3.16	-4.45	-4.77	-1.89	-2.45	-1.63	-0.93	-5.56	-1.52
-5.64	-5.30	-6.20	-1.01	-6.16	-7.78	-5.57	-0.68	-7.54	-3.86	-2.27	-1.97	-5.55	-5.31	-4.27	-1.04	-0.45	-4.17	-4.76	-1.65
-4.31	-4.94	-2.78	-1.40	-4.14	-1.72	-4.56	-2.99	-3.50	-6.74	-10.36	-3.21	-4.43	-4.82	-1.87	-2.51	-1.75	-0.85	-5.54	-1.36
-5.59	-5.35	-6.09	-1.04	-6.08	-7.26	-5.55	-0.69	-7.28	-3.90	-2.32	-2.03	-5.52	-5.32	-4.44	-1.07	-0.46	-3.86	-4.77	-1.72
-4.53	-5.21	-2.96	-1.39	-4.36	-1.80	-4.77	-2.67	-3.70	-6.89	-11.27	-4.27	-3.96	-5.51	-1.74	-2.80	-2.29	-0.62	-5.68	-1.06
-5.54	-5.59	-5.83	-1.17	-5.95	-5.60	-5.54	-0.75	-6.69	-4.10	-2.49	-2.29	-5.49	-5.39	-5.04	-1.18	-0.51	-3.12	-4.89	-1.95
-4.51	-5.25	-3.01	-1.67	-4.37	-1.89	-4.76	-2.46	-3.73	-6.66	-8.65	-3.68	-4.64	-4.99	-2.13	-2.66	-1.44	-1.06	-5.62	-1.81
-5.47	-5.83	-5.49	-1.32	-5.79	-4.56	-5.51	-0.82	-6.17	-4.32	-2.68	-2.59	-5.43	-5.44	-5.62	-1.34	-0.53	-2.62	-4.99	-2.23
-4.69	-5.55	-3.24	-1.82	-4.58	-2.04	-4.93	-2.07	-3.97	-6.45	-6.45	-4.02	-4.81	-5.17	-2.36	-2.68	-1.30	-1.12	-5.63	-1.97
-4.99	-6.14	-3.89	-1.95	-5.02	-2.55	-5.19	-1.38	-4.57	-5.57	-4.21	-4.30	-5.07	-5.40	-3.17	-2.27	-0.92	-1.42	-5.43	-2.53
-5.23	-6.22	-4.63	-1.70	-5.39	-3.25	-5.36	-1.04	-5.24	-4.86	-3.26	-3.39	-5.25	-5.46	-4.16	-1.74	-0.69	-1.84	-5.20	-2.61

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.30	-4.39	-2.82	-1.61	-4.12	-1.72	-4.55	-2.33	-3.48	-6.76	-9.70	-2.66	-4.45	-4.77	-0.55	-1.73	-1.68	-1.29	-5.56	-1.61
-5.64	-4.69	-6.18	-1.19	-6.16	-7.78	-5.57	-0.08	-7.54	-3.86	-2.27	-1.48	-5.55	-5.31	-2.69	-0.40	-0.49	-4.50	-4.76	-1.77
-4.31	-4.41	-2.83	-1.47	-4.14	-1.72	-4.56	-2.27	-3.50	-6.74	-10.36	-2.71	-4.43	-4.82	-0.79	-1.57	-1.86	-0.94	-5.54	-1.33
-5.59	-4.75	-6.12	-1.23	-6.08	-7.26	-5.55	-0.18	-7.28	-3.90	-2.32	-1.55	-5.52	-5.32	-3.52	-0.43	-0.50	-4.25	-4.77	-1.84
-4.53	-4.66	-3.01	-1.24	-4.36	-1.80	-4.77	-1.90	-3.70	-6.89	-11.27	-0.82	-3.96	-5.50	-2.92	-0.64	-2.77	0.16	-5.68	-0.72
-5.54	-5.01	-5.90	-1.36	-5.95	-5.60	-5.54	-0.23	-6.69	-4.10	-2.49	-1.76	-5.49	-5.39	-6.51	-0.53	-0.56	-3.57	-4.89	-2.07
-4.51	-4.72	-3.07	-1.88	-4.37	-1.89	-4.76	-1.82	-3.73	-6.66	-8.65	-3.37	-4.64	-4.99	-0.64	-2.21	-1.46	-1.51	-5.62	-1.97
-5.47	-5.25	-5.53	-1.52	-5.79	-4.56	-5.51	-0.31	-6.17	-4.32	-2.68	-2.05	-5.43	-5.44	-7.05	-0.55	-0.55	-3.15	-4.99	-2.37
-4.69	-5.01	-3.30	-1.98	-4.58	-2.04	-4.93	-1.44	-3.97	-6.45	-6.45	-4.40	-4.81	-5.17	-0.84	-2.37	-1.34	-1.50	-5.63	-2.08
-4.99	-5.57	-3.93	-2.10	-5.02	-2.55	-5.19	-0.82	-4.57	-5.57	-4.21	-5.39	-5.07	-5.40	-1.62	-1.72	-0.96	-1.83	-5.43	-2.63
-5.23	-5.63	-4.63	-1.87	-5.39	-3.25	-5.36	-0.51	-5.24	-4.86	-3.26	-3.20	-5.25	-5.46	-4.41	-1.04	-0.73	-2.27	-5.20	-2.71

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	0.18083	1	0.57059
2	0.47918	2	0.90013
3	0.15636	3	0.54426
4	0.45622	4	0.88027
5	0.32523	5	0.70374
6	0.48622	6	0.91897
7	0.24044	7	0.63499
8	0.49508	8	0.92171
9	0.33240	9	0.73691
10	0.40963	10	0.82430
11	0.44661	11	0.86176

Optimum Pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	5,288.33
3	3,647.35	8,687.53
4	177.94	62.90
5	0.00	0.00
6	920.55	803.42
7	0.00	0.00
8	0.00	381.20
9	0.00	0.00
10	0.00	0.00
11	0.00	0.00
12	0.00	950.55
13	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.00
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	0.00	0.00
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	6870.51	17397.76

Run 4

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.30	-5.11	-2.43	-1.44	-4.12	-1.70	-4.55	-3.04	-3.48	-6.76	-9.70	-3.15	-4.45	-4.77	-2.03	-2.49	-1.63	-0.93	-5.56	-1.52
-5.63	-5.50	-5.84	-1.08	-6.15	-7.74	-5.57	-0.67	-7.55	-3.84	-2.28	-1.94	-5.55	-5.31	-4.43	-1.12	-0.48	-4.19	-4.75	-1.72
-4.31	-5.13	-2.45	-1.42	-4.14	-1.70	-4.56	-2.99	-3.50	-6.74	-10.36	-3.20	-4.43	-4.82	-2.18	-2.42	-1.72	-0.87	-5.54	-1.41
-5.59	-5.56	-5.73	-1.03	-6.08	-7.21	-5.55	-0.68	-7.28	-3.91	-2.31	-2.02	-5.51	-5.32	-4.67	-1.13	-0.47	-3.86	-4.77	-1.71
-4.53	-5.40	-2.62	-1.44	-4.36	-1.80	-4.77	-2.67	-3.70	-6.89	-11.27	-4.26	-3.96	-5.51	-3.60	-1.98	-2.10	-0.71	-5.68	-1.22
-5.54	-5.80	-5.45	-1.17	-5.95	-5.56	-5.54	-0.75	-6.69	-4.10	-2.49	-2.27	-5.49	-5.39	-5.46	-1.25	-0.50	-3.12	-4.89	-1.95
-4.51	-5.44	-2.67	-1.67	-4.37	-1.87	-4.76	-2.46	-3.74	-6.66	-8.65	-3.66	-4.64	-4.99	-2.23	-2.76	-1.45	-1.05	-5.62	-1.80
-5.45	-6.03	-5.13	-1.34	-5.79	-4.54	-5.51	-0.82	-6.17	-4.31	-2.69	-2.58	-5.43	-5.44	-5.96	-1.39	-0.55	-2.60	-4.99	-2.20
-4.69	-5.74	-2.90	-1.81	-4.58	-2.02	-4.93	-2.06	-3.97	-6.45	-6.45	-3.98	-4.81	-5.17	-2.48	-2.77	-1.30	-1.12	-5.63	-1.97
-4.99	-6.35	-3.54	-1.96	-5.02	-2.53	-5.19	-1.38	-4.57	-5.57	-4.21	-4.25	-5.07	-5.40	-3.30	-2.33	-0.92	-1.42	-5.43	-2.52
-5.23	-6.43	-4.28	-1.70	-5.39	-3.24	-5.36	-1.03	-5.24	-4.86	-3.26	-3.36	-5.25	-5.46	-4.50	-1.79	-0.70	-1.84	-5.20	-2.61

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.30	-4.34	-2.95	-1.61	-4.12	-1.75	-4.55	-2.49	-3.48	-6.76	-9.70	-2.78	-4.45	-4.77	-2.09	-2.55	-1.67	-1.29	-5.56	-1.62
-5.63	-4.64	-6.33	-1.39	-6.15	-7.77	-5.57	-0.24	-7.55	-3.84	-2.28	-1.63	-5.55	-5.31	-4.51	-1.20	-0.53	-4.57	-4.75	-1.88
-4.31	-4.36	-2.96	-1.51	-4.14	-1.75	-4.56	-2.44	-3.50	-6.74	-10.36	-2.82	-4.43	-4.82	-2.28	-2.43	-1.81	-1.04	-5.54	-1.41
-5.59	-4.70	-6.27	-1.20	-6.08	-7.24	-5.55	-0.30	-7.28	-3.91	-2.31	-1.65	-5.51	-5.32	-4.75	-1.20	-0.51	-4.23	-4.77	-1.83
-4.53	-4.62	-3.14	-1.37	-4.36	-1.84	-4.77	-2.07	-3.70	-6.89	-11.27	-1.49	-3.96	-5.50	-3.97	-1.73	-2.47	-0.22	-5.68	-1.00
-5.54	-4.96	-6.05	-1.36	-5.95	-5.60	-5.54	-0.36	-6.69	-4.10	-2.49	-1.89	-5.49	-5.39	-5.51	-1.32	-0.54	-3.57	-4.89	-2.06
-4.51	-4.67	-3.20	-1.86	-4.37	-1.91	-4.76	-1.97	-3.74	-6.66	-8.65	-3.46	-4.64	-4.99	-2.29	-2.83	-1.47	-1.48	-5.62	-1.93
-5.45	-5.20	-5.68	-1.56	-5.79	-4.59	-5.51	-0.44	-6.17	-4.31	-2.69	-2.18	-5.43	-5.44	-6.00	-1.47	-0.59	-3.08	-4.99	-2.33
-4.69	-4.96	-3.44	-1.98	-4.58	-2.07	-4.93	-1.59	-3.97	-6.45	-6.45	-4.40	-4.81	-5.17	-2.55	-2.84	-1.34	-1.50	-5.63	-2.08
-4.99	-5.52	-4.07	-2.12	-5.02	-2.58	-5.19	-0.96	-4.57	-5.57	-4.21	-5.29	-5.07	-5.40	-3.37	-2.40	-0.96	-1.84	-5.43	-2.62
-5.23	-5.58	-4.78	-1.87	-5.39	-3.28	-5.36	-0.64	-5.24	-4.86	-3.26	-3.29	-5.25	-5.46	-4.56	-1.86	-0.74	-2.28	-5.20	-2.71

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	0.18091	1	0.59836
2	0.47999	2	0.93303
3	0.15650	3	0.57212
4	0.45664	4	0.90978
5	0.32743	5	0.73701
6	0.48729	6	0.94148
7	0.24061	7	0.66235
8	0.49593	8	0.94460
9	0.33265	9	0.76368
10	0.40982	10	0.85195
11	0.44747	11	0.88740

Optimum Pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	5,532.70
3	4,116.89	8,534.78
4	177.94	62.90
5	0.00	0.00
6	920.55	920.55
7	0.00	0.00
8	0.00	381.20
9	0.00	0.00
10	0.00	0.00
11	0.00	0.00
12	0.00	950.55
13	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.00
15	426.64	349.11
16	617.43	417.99
17	356.78	223.67
18	561.10	140.08
19	0.00	0.00
20	162.73	92.96
Total pumping rate	7,340.05	17,606.50

For $H_{ref} = 6.48$ m

Run 1

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.27	-4.60	-3.53	-1.48	-4.12	-1.72	-4.55	-3.06	-3.48	-6.76	-9.70	-3.31	-4.45	-4.77	-2.05	-2.51	-1.63	-1.00	-5.56	-1.56
-5.63	-4.93	-7.03	-1.05	-6.16	-7.78	-5.60	-0.71	-7.57	-3.84	-2.28	-2.14	-5.55	-5.31	-4.45	-1.13	-0.47	-4.28	-4.76	-1.68
-4.29	-4.62	-3.55	-1.50	-4.14	-1.74	-4.56	-3.02	-3.50	-6.74	-10.36	-3.35	-4.43	-4.82	-2.03	-2.57	-1.61	-1.02	-5.54	-1.58
-5.59	-4.99	-6.96	-1.08	-6.08	-7.26	-5.55	-0.76	-7.27	-3.91	-2.31	-2.22	-5.51	-5.32	-4.71	-1.16	-0.48	-3.94	-4.77	-1.75
-4.50	-4.89	-3.77	-1.61	-4.36	-1.86	-4.77	-2.70	-3.70	-6.89	-11.27	-4.42	-3.96	-5.51	-1.91	-2.87	-1.44	-1.15	-5.68	-1.73
-5.53	-5.25	-6.72	-1.21	-5.95	-5.60	-5.54	-0.82	-6.69	-4.10	-2.49	-2.45	-5.49	-5.39	-5.54	-1.27	-0.52	-3.17	-4.89	-1.98
-4.49	-4.93	-3.80	-1.68	-4.37	-1.88	-4.76	-2.49	-3.73	-6.66	-8.65	-3.88	-4.64	-4.99	-2.28	-2.75	-1.48	-1.09	-5.62	-1.78
-5.45	-5.49	-6.35	-1.35	-5.80	-4.56	-5.51	-0.89	-6.18	-4.32	-2.69	-2.74	-5.43	-5.45	-6.02	-1.41	-0.56	-2.65	-4.99	-2.22
-4.67	-5.23	-4.05	-1.84	-4.58	-2.04	-4.93	-2.11	-3.97	-6.45	-6.45	-4.43	-4.81	-5.17	-2.51	-2.81	-1.31	-1.18	-5.63	-2.00
-4.98	-5.79	-4.71	-2.01	-5.02	-2.55	-5.19	-1.44	-4.57	-5.57	-4.21	-4.86	-5.07	-5.40	-3.32	-2.36	-0.93	-1.49	-5.43	-2.58
-5.21	-5.85	-5.44	-1.73	-5.39	-3.25	-5.36	-1.10	-5.24	-4.86	-3.26	-3.65	-5.25	-5.46	-4.56	-1.81	-0.71	-1.90	-5.20	-2.68

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.27	-4.60	-3.53	-1.48	-4.12	-1.72	-4.55	-3.06	-3.48	-6.76	-9.70	-3.31	-4.45	-4.77	-2.05	-2.51	-1.63	-1.00	-5.56	-1.56
-5.63	-4.93	-7.03	-1.05	-6.16	-7.78	-5.60	-0.71	-7.57	-3.85	-2.28	-2.14	-5.56	-5.31	-4.45	-1.13	-0.47	-4.28	-4.76	-1.68
-4.29	-4.62	-3.55	-1.50	-4.14	-1.74	-4.56	-3.02	-3.50	-6.74	-10.36	-3.35	-4.43	-4.82	-2.03	-2.57	-1.61	-1.02	-5.54	-1.58
-5.59	-4.99	-6.96	-1.08	-6.08	-7.26	-5.55	-0.76	-7.27	-3.91	-2.31	-2.22	-5.51	-5.32	-4.71	-1.16	-0.48	-3.94	-4.77	-1.75
-4.50	-4.89	-3.77	-1.61	-4.36	-1.86	-4.77	-2.70	-3.70	-6.89	-11.27	-4.42	-3.96	-5.50	-1.91	-2.87	-1.44	-1.15	-5.68	-1.73
-5.53	-5.25	-6.72	-1.21	-5.95	-5.60	-5.54	-0.82	-6.69	-4.10	-2.49	-2.45	-5.49	-5.39	-5.54	-1.27	-0.52	-3.17	-4.89	-1.98
-4.49	-4.93	-3.80	-1.68	-4.37	-1.88	-4.76	-2.49	-3.73	-6.66	-8.65	-3.88	-4.64	-4.99	-2.28	-2.75	-1.48	-1.09	-5.61	-1.78
-5.45	-5.49	-6.35	-1.35	-5.80	-4.56	-5.51	-0.89	-6.18	-4.32	-2.69	-2.74	-5.43	-5.45	-6.02	-1.41	-0.56	-2.65	-4.99	-2.22
-4.67	-5.23	-4.05	-1.84	-4.58	-2.04	-4.93	-2.11	-3.97	-6.45	-6.45	-4.43	-4.81	-5.17	-2.51	-2.81	-1.31	-1.18	-5.63	-2.00
-4.98	-5.79	-4.71	-2.01	-5.02	-2.55	-5.19	-1.44	-4.57	-5.57	-4.21	-4.86	-5.07	-5.40	-3.32	-2.36	-0.93	-1.49	-5.43	-2.58
-5.21	-5.85	-5.44	-1.73	-5.39	-3.25	-5.36	-1.10	-5.24	-4.86	-3.26	-3.65	-5.25	-5.46	-4.56	-1.81	-0.71	-1.90	-5.20	-2.68

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	0.02575	1	0.395884
2	0.330789	2	0.734381
3	0.001448	3	0.370089
4	0.309786	4	0.711123
5	0.172736	5	0.549808
6	0.341875	6	0.741935
7	0.086662	7	0.459067
8	0.347519	8	0.74503
9	0.181407	9	0.558718
10	0.261845	10	0.645317
11	0.297572	11	0.686835

Optimum Pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	0.00	0.00
2	0.00	0.00
3	0.00	7,231.18
4	0.00	62.90
5	0.00	0.00
6	0.00	920.55
7	0.00	0.00
8	0.00	381.20
9	0.00	815.75
10	0.00	0.00
11	0.00	0.00
12	0.00	950.55
13	0.00	0.00
14	0.00	0.00
15	0.00	349.11
16	0.00	417.99
17	0.00	223.67
18	141.77	140.08
19	0.00	0.00
20	0.00	92.96
Total pumping rate	141.77	11,585.95

Run 2

Response Matrix for the Dry Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.30	-4.59	-3.80	-1.42	-4.12	-1.55	-4.55	-3.04	-3.05	-6.76	-9.70	-3.17	-4.45	-4.77	-1.90	-2.46	-1.62	-0.86	-5.56	-1.48
-5.67	-4.93	-7.31	-0.99	-6.15	-7.25	-5.61	-0.69	-7.08	-3.87	-2.27	-1.99	-5.55	-5.31	-4.28	-1.04	-0.43	-4.00	-4.76	-1.61
-4.31	-4.61	-3.82	-1.45	-4.14	-1.56	-4.56	-2.99	-3.07	-6.74	-10.36	-3.22	-4.43	-4.82	-1.88	-2.52	-1.60	-1.39	-5.54	-1.51
-5.60	-4.99	-7.25	-1.02	-6.09	-6.76	-5.55	-0.70	-6.83	-3.90	-2.32	-2.05	-5.52	-5.31	-4.45	-1.07	-0.44	-3.72	-4.77	-1.68
-4.53	-4.88	-4.04	-1.57	-4.36	-1.68	-4.77	-2.68	-3.26	-6.89	-11.27	-4.28	-3.96	-5.51	-1.75	-2.81	-1.42	-3.21	-5.68	-1.66
-5.54	-5.24	-7.03	-1.15	-5.95	-5.20	-5.54	-0.75	-6.23	-4.10	-2.49	-2.30	-5.49	-5.39	-5.06	-1.19	-0.48	-3.05	-4.89	-1.91
-4.51	-4.93	-4.08	-1.64	-4.37	-1.70	-4.76	-2.46	-3.29	-6.66	-8.65	-3.69	-4.64	-4.99	-2.13	-2.66	-1.46	-0.77	-5.62	-1.71
-5.47	-5.48	-6.64	-1.30	-5.79	-4.34	-5.51	-0.82	-5.70	-4.32	-2.68	-2.60	-5.43	-5.44	-5.63	-1.34	-0.53	-2.39	-4.99	-2.14
-4.69	-5.23	-4.33	-1.80	-4.58	-1.86	-4.93	-2.07	-3.51	-6.45	-6.45	-4.05	-4.81	-5.17	-2.36	-2.69	-1.29	-1.02	-5.63	-1.94
-4.99	-5.79	-4.99	-1.92	-5.02	-2.36	-5.19	-1.38	-4.10	-5.57	-4.21	-4.35	-5.07	-5.40	-3.18	-2.27	-0.90	-1.31	-5.43	-2.44
-5.23	-5.85	-5.72	-1.68	-5.39	-3.09	-5.36	-1.04	-4.76	-4.86	-3.26	-3.41	-5.25	-5.46	-4.18	-1.74	-0.68	-1.75	-5.20	-2.52

Response Matrix for the Wet Season

$\frac{\partial H_i}{\partial Q_j} * 10^{-5}$																			
-4.30	-4.59	-3.35	3.45	-4.12	-0.77	-4.55	-2.01	-0.78	-6.76	-9.70	-2.43	-4.45	-4.77	0.11	-1.39	-0.61	-0.77	-5.56	2.70
-5.67	-4.93	-6.81	4.59	-6.15	-8.67	-5.61	0.25	-4.36	-3.87	-2.27	-1.22	-5.55	-5.31	-1.92	-0.09	0.38	-4.12	-4.76	3.37
-4.31	-4.61	-3.37	3.66	-4.14	-0.77	-4.56	-1.95	-0.77	-6.74	-10.36	-2.47	-4.43	-4.82	-0.24	-1.14	-0.90	-0.25	-5.54	3.18
-5.60	-4.99	-6.74	4.02	-6.09	-8.01	-5.55	0.16	-4.02	-3.90	-2.32	-1.31	-5.52	-5.31	-2.98	-0.12	0.38	-3.74	-4.77	3.28
-4.53	-4.88	-3.57	4.21	-4.36	-0.81	-4.77	-1.54	-0.84	-6.89	-11.27	0.50	-3.96	-5.50	-3.36	0.33	-2.37	1.46	-5.68	4.44
-5.54	-5.24	-6.51	4.18	-5.95	-5.29	-5.54	0.02	-3.48	-4.10	-2.49	-1.51	-5.49	-5.39	-6.94	-0.21	0.32	-2.90	-4.89	3.02
-4.51	-4.93	-3.62	3.21	-4.37	-0.92	-4.76	-1.53	-0.99	-6.66	-8.65	-3.18	-4.64	-4.99	0.08	-1.98	-0.47	-1.05	-5.62	2.64
-5.47	-5.48	-6.14	4.06	-5.79	-3.55	-5.51	-0.06	-3.02	-4.32	-2.68	-1.80	-5.43	-5.44	-7.51	-0.18	0.35	-2.50	-4.99	2.36
-4.69	-5.23	-3.86	2.89	-4.58	-1.05	-4.93	-1.15	-1.16	-6.45	-6.45	-4.38	-4.81	-5.17	-0.10	-2.18	-0.40	-0.97	-5.63	2.68
-4.99	-5.79	-4.51	1.46	-5.02	-1.49	-5.19	-0.55	-1.67	-5.57	-4.21	-5.58	-5.07	-5.40	-0.87	-1.44	-0.03	-1.26	-5.43	0.16
-5.23	-5.85	-5.23	3.12	-5.39	-2.13	-5.36	-0.25	-2.23	-4.86	-3.26	-3.04	-5.25	-5.46	-4.34	-0.71	0.18	-1.65	-5.20	-0.68

Constraints Vectors

Well	b for the dry season	Well	b for the wet season
1	-0.00427	1	0.356077
2	0.295558	2	0.706347
3	-0.02776	3	0.329442
4	0.273593	4	0.684684
5	0.144959	5	0.480311
6	0.304966	6	0.717198
7	0.055155	7	0.421786
8	0.313189	8	0.715388
9	0.147915	9	0.526501
10	0.226918	10	0.620262
11	0.264338	11	0.657228

Optimum Pumping Rates

Pumping Well	Q for the Dry Season (m ³ /day)	Q for the Wet Season (m ³ /day)
1	-	0.00
2	-	201.28
3	-	8,109.21
4	-	62.90
5	-	0.00
6	-	920.55
7	-	0.00
8	-	381.20
9	-	815.75
10	-	0.00
11	-	0.00
12	-	950.55
13	-	0.00
14	-	0.00
15	-	349.11
16	-	417.99
17	-	223.67
18	-	140.08
19	-	0.00
20	-	92.96
Total pumping rate	-	12,665.26